

POLITICAL MIGRATION TO CITY OF KORONADAL OF MARAWI SIEGE BAKWITS: SEEN THROUGH THE LENS OF RAVENSTEIN

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ABSTRACT

The inception of Marawi Siege in 2017 demonstrated the significant influence of politics on migration trends highlighting how political instability and exploitation of local grievances can push families to seek shelter in safer areas. This phenomenon needs in-depth investigation as it can be extremely beneficial in understanding the larger social, economic, and political implications of forced displacement in the Philippines. The study utilized instrumental qualitative case study to gain an insider's view on the case of six bakwits and provide insight to the political migration phenomenon. The data were generated from semi-structured interviews and analyzed through the lens of Ravenstein's Theory of Migration. The study reveals the dual nature of migration through push factors present in the place of origin like violence and pull factors such as safety in their place of destination. The trauma of displacement and loss of livelihoods were among the many difficulties bakwits faced during their political migration. They overcame these difficulties by forming community networks, relying on family support, and exhibiting resilience through cooperation and resourcefulness. The findings also illustrate that the bakwits not only escaped danger but also found opportunities for economic growth and education, emphasizing a more nuanced view of migration that goes beyond mere reaction to crises. The findings suggest that policymakers should prioritize conflict resolution and community stabilization initiatives in areas prone to violence. Furthermore, interventions must be modified to identify and capitalize on the strengths of bakwits, fostering their agency and motivating them to actively engage in their new communities.

Keywords: political migration, *Marawi Siege*, *bakwits*, *factors*, *challenges*, *coping strategies*, *opportunities*, *migration theory*

INTRODUCTION

Migration is an integral part of daily life. People move for a variety of reasons, including seeking new opportunities, earning higher wages, reuniting with loved ones, escaping social or political difficulties, studying, and among others (Kynsilehto, 2022). Migration studies have traditionally emphasized pull and push factors when explaining mobilities (Lee, 1966).

Political migration is a complicated and diverse phenomenon that takes many forms. One of its most common forms is political which includes case like that of refugees, who leave their home countries in response to acts of violence, war, or political persecution. The need for safety and protection drives these migrants to frequently apply for asylum in nearby nations or regions (Niva et al., 2023).

Another type of migrants are the dissidents and activists who flee their home countries in order to avoid repression or to carry on with their advocacy work in a more conducive environment. Moreover, political and economic factors may interact to cause migration that is motivated by the need to flee oppression or unstable political environments as well as the desire for greater economic opportunities.

In the recent years, events such as 2017 Marawi Siege resulted in political migration of Marawi residents to other parts of the country. The predominantly Muslim population of Marawi City, which is part of the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), and the region's complicated history of conflict and autonomy have shaped the city's distinct political environment (International Crisis Group, n.d.). Muslim rebels seeking independence or autonomy have long been at odds with the central government, which wants to keep control of the southern islands. This conflict has long existed in the city. Despite the region's natural riches, it is essentially undeveloped and politically unstable as a result of this conflict.

A turning point in the history of the Philippines, the Marawi Siege profoundly affected the lives of thousands of people who were forced to flee their homes. Due to the conflict, a sizable population of internally displaced people (IDPs), also known as Marawi Siege *bakwits*, have fled to different parts of the nation, including City of Koronadal.

The political migration of these *bakwits* to City of Koronadal is a phenomenon that needs in-depth investigation as researchers have identified that there is a knowledge gap on this topic. Many of these displaced people have sought to rebuild their lives in the City of Koronadal located in the southern part of the Philippines which eventually became a hub for them. By the virtue of former President Gloria Macapagal-Arroyo, through the Executive Order No. 304 released on March 30, 2004, City of Koronadal was designated as the regional center and seat of SOCCSKSARGEN region and all departments, bureaus, and offices of the national government in Cotabato City were transferred to its new regional seat of operations. Gaining knowledge of these migration's dynamics, the difficulties the *bakwits* encountered, and their assimilation into the local community can

be extremely beneficial in understanding the larger social, economic, and political implications of forced displacement.

The Lens: Political Migration Theory

The laws of migration, as proposed by Ravenstein in 1885, explained the variables affecting patterns of migration, including political migration. Ravenstein identified push and pull factors as the main driving forces behind migration, and these factors are at the center of his framework. Push factors, as they relate to political migration, are those aspects of the home country that compel individuals or groups to migrate, whereas pull factors are those aspects of the destination country that attract migrants.

Political elements including persecution, political repression, and wars have an impact on political migration, according to Ravenstein's theory. These motivators force people or communities to seek shelter or asylum in safer or more politically stable areas. Ravenstein's viewpoint highlights the importance of political instability and governance failures in driving migration, emphasizing the interaction of political, economic, and social issues.

Economic reasons are critical in political migration, according to Ravenstein's paradigm. Economic challenges, such as unemployment, poverty, and a lack of economic possibilities, can intensify political discontent and influence migratory decisions. In nations with more stable political systems, people may migrate in search of greater economic opportunities, seeing it as a way to better their lives and provide a brighter future for their families.

Social forces interact with political reasons to shape migration trends. Political grievances can be exacerbated by social exclusion, discrimination, and marginalization, which lead people to go to nations where their rights are more protected and they are more likely to be socially included. Decisions about migration may also be influenced by social networks and attachments to the community, as people look for assistance and camaraderie while overcoming the difficulties of displacement.

A fundamental understanding of the intricate motives underlying migration decisions and the interdependence of push and pull variables may be gained from Ravenstein's views on political migration. His theoretical approach still guides current migration research, emphasizing how crucial it is to take into account the complex dynamics of political movement. Policymakers and academics can create more effective plans for tackling the underlying causes of migration and advancing inclusive and sustainable solutions for migrants and refugees by looking at the interaction of economic, social, and political issues.

Categories of Migration: Forced Migration and Voluntary Migration

There are two primary categories of human migration that have existed for centuries: forced migration and voluntary migration (Lech, 2020). She defines forced migration as the movement of people or groups who are compelled to leave their homes because of events like natural disasters, war, persecution, or development projects. On the other hand, voluntary migration occurs when individuals or organizations consciously choose to leave their hometown and migrate to a new area.

While forced migration refers to situations in which individuals or groups are compelled to leave their homes—often against their will—due to uncontrollable external circumstances, voluntary migration is a more intentional and voluntary decision made by people or groups for reasons such as social and cultural norms, political stability, or economic opportunities. Desperate situations and a desire to escape imminent danger or threats usually result in forced migration. In contrast, the motivation behind voluntary migration stems from individual aspirations for a better life.

Types of Migration: Internal Migration and External Migration

The movement of people or groups across borders is known as migration, and it is a complicated and multidimensional phenomenon with significant social, economic, and political implications. Internal migration and external migration are the two main types of migration. Internal migration refers to the movement of people within a nation, while external migration is the movement of people across national borders. Both types of migration are intricate and multidimensional phenomenon that have a big impact on the political, social, and economic structures of the societies involved.

The vast bulk of worldwide migration, estimated at 763 million people, takes place within a country's boundaries rather than across them. Families and people looking to enhance their socioeconomic circumstances are primarily responsible for this trend; they frequently do this by relocating from rural to urban regions in pursuit of opportunities and improved economic prospects (FAO, 2023). Many academic fields have contributed to the development of theories of migration, which contend that social and economic variables at different geographic scales have a significant impact on both internal and external migration (White & Lindstrom, 2019). As an example, studies have demonstrated that there are frequently close connections between internal and international migration as the two categories of mobility can logically and conceptually converge (Hugo, 2016; White & Lindstrom, 2019).

Classification of Migrants: Permanent Migrant and Temporary Migrant

People migrate when they relocate from one geographic area to another for a variety of reasons, including experiences and motivations. Within this broad spectrum, there is a fundamental distinction between temporary and permanent migration. While temporary migration entails moving for a set period of time with the goal of eventually returning to their place of origin, permanent migration is moving with the idea of settling down permanently in the new environment. Every type of migration has unique financial, social, and legal implications for the migrant community as well as the nations of origin.

Moving oneself or one's family to a new nation or area with the intention of settling there permanently is known as permanent migration. According to Hall (2011), family reunification, political unrest, and economic possibilities are some of the main causes of this type of migration. While retaining significant links, transnational migrants may reside in two locations simultaneously or at least travel between them often.

The Context: Marawi City and People of Lake Lanao

Situated in the southern Philippines' Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), Marawi City serves as a significant hub for Maranao culture and history. The geographical significance of Marawi is highlighted by its center location in Lanao del Sur Province, where it serves as a significant hub for trade, education, and religious activities. This importance is further underscored by the impact of the 'Battle of Marawi,' which lasted between May and October 2017, resulting in substantial destruction and loss of life (Amnesty International, 2022). The city's strategic location on the northern edge of Lake Lanao has contributed to its growth as a commercial and cultural center, drawing people from a variety of backgrounds and fostering cross-cultural interaction. Furthermore, Marawi's significance as a symbol of Maranao identity and tenacity is highlighted by its rich cultural past, which includes distinctive Islamic architecture, and traditional crafts.

Centuries of history and tradition have shaped the rich cultural legacy of the indigenous Maranao people of the Philippines. Baddiri's reflections demonstrate how the Bangsamoro community's cultural identity and historical struggles have shaped it profoundly. He highlights the profound effects of the war on their social structures, economic circumstances, and collective psyche. Islam is the foundation of the Bangsamoro people's rich cultural heritage, which is evident in their customs and social bonds. Furthermore, the continuous difficulties they encounter in claiming their rights and identity in a country that is primarily Christian underscore the intricacies of their past governance and the pursuit of self-determination. This story emphasizes how crucial it is to comprehend their distinct role in the larger framework of Philippine society (Baddiri, 2007).

The Maranao historically governed themselves using a datuship system in which regional leaders, or datu, had jurisdiction over their respective territories. The original Moro, especially Maranao, government structure is described by Fianza (2004) as a decentralized one in which regional chiefs, or datu, oversaw their own areas. The research demonstrates how the Maranao's pre-colonial political structures were firmly based on local practices and customary laws, giving them a solid basis for government. However, these native forms of government were severely upset by the entry of foreign powers. The Maranao showed resilience in the face of these difficulties by preserving their traditional identity and political systems.

Marawi City's political landscape is shaped by both contemporary forces and historical legacies, reflecting broader themes of identity, conflict, and governance in the Philippines. The substantial effects of armed conflict on Marawi's internally displaced people's (IDPs') safety and security. It emphasizes how the region's militarization exacerbates vulnerabilities, particularly for women and other marginalized groups who face increased risks of gender-based violence in the face of persistent instability. These IDPs' stories demonstrate the complex interaction of local and national factors and are strongly tied to Mindanao's larger historical background of violence and displacement. The essay goes on to emphasize the critical need for focused interventions and policies that put impacted communities' safety and empowerment first, especially in the pursuit of regional peace and sustainable development (Veloso, 2022).

Marawi City, which embodies the enduring customs and goals of the Maranao people, is significant both physically and culturally. Marawi is a significant example of the difficulties faced by local communities striving for stability and reconciliation, as its residents continue to navigate the aftermath of violence while striving for a future marked by peace and development. The Battle of Marawi highlights the crucial implications of the conflict for the region's stalled peace process, highlighting how the intense fighting not only exacerbated existing tensions among ethnic groups but also brought to light the vulnerabilities of the peace framework established for Mindanao. The resilience of the Marawi people reflects their enduring commitment to fostering unity and addressing the deep-rooted issues that threaten their aspirations for a peaceful coexistence (Center for Strategic and International Studies, 2017).

Apotheosis: 2017 Marawi Siege

The Maute Group, associated with ISIS, violently seized control of Marawi City in 2017, highlighting the significance of the Marawi Siege in Philippine history. According to Amnesty International (2017), about 360,000 people in Marawi and surrounding areas were displaced due to the conflict. The Maute Group is a radical Islamist organization that seeks to create a caliphate in the southern Philippines. The origins of the Maute Group and their strategic goals during the siege of Marawi are thoroughly examined by Hwang (2019). After the five months of intense fighting, which left Marawi City in ruins and forced many of its citizens to flee, the Maute Group took advantage of the chaos to take control of key urban areas and elicited strong opposition from government forces. As the situation worsened, military operations included aerial bombardments directed at the group's strongholds in an attempt to retake the city and restore order amid the chaos. This conflict period brought to light the intricacies of urban warfare and the consequences for both local communities and national security.

There were several factors that drove the Maute Group's effort to take over Marawi City, including politics, socioeconomics, and ideology. According to Hwang (2019), the socioeconomic conditions and family networks in Mindanao were closely related to the reasons behind the formation of the Maute Group and its hiring procedures. Omar and Abdullah Maute, the group's leaders, used pre-existing frustrations within the poor Muslim community to mobilize support and increase their power. Their recruitment tactics frequently relied on personal connections; many members joined because they already had family or friends, which encouraged devotion and dedication to the group's goals.

The Marawi Siege had profound effects on culture, politics, and the economy. A modification of counterterrorism tactics and peacebuilding programs was prompted by the political revelations made during the siege, which exposed the vulnerabilities of the Philippine government and security system. Marawi's economy suffered greatly as a result of the population shift and infrastructure destruction, which made poverty worse and hindered efforts for recovery.

With an emphasis on the disintegration of social institutions, relocation, and the loss of cultural identity, Wapaño (2024) investigates the significant psychological and sociocultural effects of the Marawi siege on the Meranao people. In order to assist the impacted communities in recovering and starting anew, the research emphasizes the significance of taking a comprehensive strategy to recovery that includes not just political

and economic actions but also cultural rehabilitation. Many Meranao people, who were once known as "the people of the lake," were compelled to relocate around the Philippines after the siege, becoming internally displaced persons (IDPs) and thereafter known as "Marawi Siege bakwits."

Marawi Siege Bakwits

The term "bakwit" gained popularity with the frequent use of various media outlets during the Marawi Siege to describe those who were forced to flee their homes due to the fighting. In its analysis of the current state of internally displaced people (IDPs) in the Philippines, especially in the wake of the Marawi crisis, IDMC (2024) emphasizes the government's initiatives as well as the intricate difficulties that still face individuals who have been displaced. The phrase "internally displaced persons" describes people who have been displaced by conflict but are still inside their nation's boundaries, highlighting their particular vulnerability and the need for ongoing assistance. Internally displaced people are defined by the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) as any individual or group of individuals who have been compelled to leave their homes due to natural or man-made hazards, but have not crossed an internationally recognized border. The term "bakwit," which refers to the situation of internally displaced people (IDPs), also highlights the tenacity and ingenuity of individuals impacted by the siege of Marawi. Bakwit people have a number of financial, cultural, and psychological traits in common that influence how they experience relocation.

The bakwits are resilient and have a strong sense of community; they frequently turn to their family networks for assistance when they are struggling. Their survival and coping mechanisms in the face of hardship depend on this interdependence. bakwits' socioeconomic backgrounds vary, with many hailing from low-income families, which affects their access to resources and chances for rehabilitation (Hwang, 2019). Despite their differences, bakwits are defined by their shared experiences of trauma, relocation, and uncertainty, which have shaped their coping mechanisms and identities.

According to the memorandum made by the DSWD, IDPs are grouped into two classifications based on the place where they are temporary accommodated. The classifications are those evacuation centers evacuees and home-based evacuees. Although the two classification of evacuees have the same status wherein they are provided of temporary shelter, those who belong to evacuation centers are those who temporary stay in a planned camp prepared by the government utilizing public facilities whereas home-based evacuees are those who chose to stay with their family relatives. Hwang (2019) draws attention to the stigma attached to the term "bakwit," showing how it frequently has negative connotations for those who were displaced by the siege of Marawi: Many bakwits experience social exclusion and marginalization, which can result in perceptions of them as burdens or victims without agency, which can severely impede their access to necessary services and support, further compounding their isolation; additionally, the label "bakwit" can arouse feelings of guilt and discomfort among displaced people, making it more difficult for them to assert their rights and maintain dignity in a setting characterized by discrimination and misunderstanding. These factors highlight the need for a nuanced understanding of their experiences and the difficulties they face when reintegrating into society.

In order to counter the negative connotations associated with the term "bakwit," a multifaceted strategy that dispels prejudices and encourages inclusive narratives is required. This should highlight the need of giving bakwits the opportunity to regain agency and voice by fighting for their rights and involvement in political processes. Furthermore, changing the conversation about displacement requires recognizing the tenacity, strength, and humanity of bakwits, who continue to rebuild their lives and communities in the wake of conflict and tragedy. Policymakers and humanitarian actors can create a more supportive environment for displaced people by encouraging community solidarity and empathy as well as challenging the stigma associated with the term "bakwit."

City of Koronadal as a Place of Destination for Bakwits

Executive Order No. 304, issued in 2004, designated City of Koronadal as the regional center for SOCCSKSARGEN Region (Region XII) to improve governance and service delivery. The order required national government agencies to relocate their operations to Koronadal. While many agencies successfully transferred, some faced challenges, such as funding and logistical issues. The move has been met with mixed reactions: Koronadal benefits from centralized governance, but other areas, like Cotabato City, have expressed concerns about the economic impact.

The City of Koronadal, which is in the heart of South Cotabato, has seen tremendous economic expansion recently, drawing immigrants looking for better employment and financial opportunities. One of City of Koronadal's primary attractions is the expanding local economy. Both skilled and unskilled individuals can find plenty of employment opportunities in its growing industries, which are mostly in manufacturing, retail, and agriculture. In addition to creating jobs, the existence of business centers and infrastructure upgrades such shopping centers, metro systems, and markets attracts investors and entrepreneurs (City Government of Koronadal, 2020).

A key component of Koronadal's economy is the agricultural sector, which employs vast areas of land to produce goods including vegetables, corn, and rice. For people from rural areas seeking better farming and agribusiness prospects, this makes the city a desirable destination (Tañada, 2021). Further drawing in those looking to capitalize on its expanding market is City of Koronadal's role as the Soccsksargen region's regional center for trade and commerce (Philippine Statistics Authority, 2022).

City of Koronadal has been a major economic hub in South Cotabato, attracting migrants seeking better economic and employment opportunities. As a commercial and service hub, it benefits from a strategic position, upgraded infrastructure, and a welcoming corporate environment. The City Administration of Koronadal (2023) claims that the local administration has put in place a number of measures to promote investment, including expediting corporate procedures and providing incentives. Increased employment prospects have resulted from these efforts in industries like retail, services, and agriculture (City Government of Koronadal, 2023).

Additionally, The Public Employment Service Office (PESO) in City of Koronadal is essential in matching job searchers with openings. In order to help both locals and migrants locate acceptable jobs, PESO works with a number of government organizations to offer timely labor market information, career counseling, and job matching.

As Koronadal's service industries continue to grow, the local government has concentrated on developing workforce skill-building initiatives. Due to the growing need for qualified personnel in the business process outsourcing (BPO) sector, the city is establishing itself as a new center for business and IT outsourcing, providing excellent employment prospects for qualified individuals (City Government of Koronadal, 2022).

City of Koronadal has seen the creation of jobs and the attraction of both domestic and foreign investors due to the local government's proactive approach to development, which includes tax incentives for enterprises and steps to make doing business easier. Governor Tamayo highlighted in 2024 that the province's investments in local industry and infrastructure had produced over 10,000 job opportunities for locals, highlighting the region's growing economic stability (South Cotabato News, 2024).

Notable political changes have occurred recently in City of Koronadal, the capital of South Cotabato in Mindanao, Philippines. Officially joining the Partido Federal ng Pilipinas (PFP) in September 2024, Mayor Eliordo U. Ogena sided with the party's national president, South Cotabato Governor Reynaldo S. Tamayo Jr.. This action demonstrated a closer partnership between the province's and city's leadership, promoting a cordial working relationship with the goal of shared development and advancement (South Cotabato News, 2024).

The political climate of Koronadal was further influenced by the local elections in 2022. PDP-Laban party representative Mayor Ogena defeated PFP City Councilor Mylene Bascon-De Guzman to win a second term. Furthermore, six of the members of the PDP-Laban Party were elected to seat in the municipal council, giving the party a majority. The administration's policies and programs were easier to implement thanks to this majority (City Government of Koronadal, 2022).

The improvement of the city's business climate has been a top priority for Mayor Ogena's administration. In October 2023, he reaffirmed the city's commitment to improving its business climate in order to draw in investments. Among the initiatives were the installation of streetlights and the clearing of Blok Creek to create an environment that is favorable for business opportunities and economic recovery (City Government of Koronadal, 2023).

The city's pro-business policies demonstrated additional efforts to attract investors. To establish a business-friendly environment, the administration cut taxes and expedited business registration procedures, positioning Koronadal as a competitive location for both domestic and foreign investments . These political efforts and developments are indicative of City of Koronadal's dynamic political environment, which is marked by proactive governance centered on economic development and growth as well as strategic alliances (City Government of Koronadal, 2023).

Difficulties of Internally Displaced Persons

Due to conflicts, natural disasters, or other humanitarian crises, millions of people have been forced to evacuate their homes, raising serious concerns about internal displacement in recent years. IDPs have a unique set of difficulties in contrast to other displaced groups, such as refugees. Lack of international legal protection is one of the main issues domestic displaced people confront. Refugees are accorded on certain rights

and safeguarded under international law (Lischer, 2007). The circumstances that led to IDPs displacement—conflict and political unrest, for example—may contrast dramatically from the political environment in their new places, which may provide different levels of stability or difficulties with governance (Godfrey & Tafida, 2022). Remarkably, although IDPs stay inside their nation, they sometimes do not have the same legal safeguards as refugees, which might make them more vulnerable in unfamiliar situations (Phuong, 2005).

An increase in health risks, including infectious illnesses, mental health issues, and challenges with reproductive health, has been linked to displacement. especially vulnerable populations, such as the elderly, women, and children. It can be difficult for public health to respond to the needs of internally displaced individuals due to factors including politics, culture, and transportation. Access to necessary services and resources is another issue. Individuals who experience internal displacement sometimes reside in improvised camps or transitional shelters with little access to potable water, healthcare, or education. According to Thomas et al. (2008), internal displaced people frequently encounter extra difficulties acclimating to their new surroundings, even though they confront many of the same difficulties as refugees. It was also said that it might be challenging for displaced people to assimilate into the community since they may not be familiar with the language, culture, or services available in their new area. Those who are relocated may feel lonely since they are unable to establish relationships and get necessities.

According to Zetter (2011), internally displaced people frequently experience social difficulties such marginalization and a lack of rights protection. Due to cultural differences, people could find it difficult to adjust to new surroundings, as seen by the requirement for services that are sensitive to cultural differences and the role social workers play in assisting with relocation (Ekoh et al., 2022). Furthermore, the assimilation of internally displaced persons (IDPs) into local communities is an essential component of their adaptation; yet, this undertaking is accompanied with economic and job obstacles, in addition to psychological distress that demands assistance (Krakhmalova, 2019). After being domestically uprooted, people adjust to new political, social, and cultural contexts. These variations may show up as less legal safeguards, difficulties integrating into society, and the requirement for targeted support to deal with the emotional and practical effects of relocation (Krakhmalova, 2019; Phuong, 2005).

Internally Displaced People’s Coping Mechanisms

Individuals who have been considered as IDPs utilize several coping strategies to adapt to their new surroundings. The context of relocation, the available resources, and the resilience of the person all influence the coping mechanisms used by internally displaced people. Research has demonstrated that in order to cope with their situations, IDPs need both social support and problem-solving techniques (Peevey et al., 2022). IDPs in Nigeria have been seen to use traditional medicine and general finances to help them deal with health shocks, but they still face obstacles including dirty toilets and the possibility of open defecation (Samuel & Ezeah, 2020). It has been demonstrated that psychological treatments, such psycho-correction programs, help IDPs experience less anxiety and sadness by fostering adaptive coping mechanisms and enhancing resilience (Maruta et al., 2020).

Akhunzada et al. (2015) state that although some IDPs exhibit resilience and problem-solving skills, others may struggle with serious mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder that can make it difficult for them to cope. The way that youngsters and the elderly adjust to new situations is also influenced by sociodemographic parameters, such as age and socioeconomic status; important aspects that determine how well they deal are their mental and psychological states (Yurkiv & Lukanov, 2021). Also, it is emphasized that in order to assist IDPs in their coping mechanisms, social services, such as social rehabilitation and adaptation programs, must be made available (Pesotska, 2022).

By these initiatives, displaced individuals make new connections both inside and outside of their communities and use their own resources and skills to turn difficult situations into their new realities. For a number of causes, IDPs sometimes face substantial difficulties adjusting to their new surroundings. These include issues with work and housing, monetary difficulties, and the breakup of familial relationships (Krakhmalova, 2019). These problems are made worse by the absence of government assistance, which does not even cover the price of basic housing, forcing IDPs to bear the expense of housing rent and utilities, which take up almost all of their income (Krakhmalova, 2019). Furthermore, the psychological effects of relocation, which are marked by lowered resilience, elevated anxiety, and moderately severe depression, impede the process of adapting (Maruta et al., 2020).

As an example, Godfrey and Tafida (2022) report that political instability and violence are the primary causes of displacement in Plateau State, Nigeria. Schultz et al. (2014) remark that in Colombia, there are difficulties in involving IDPs in programs. Further hindering their capacity to adapt and reconstruct their life is the absence of a particular legislative framework to meet the requirements of IDPs, as observed in Pakistan (Baig et al., 2024). This can result in challenges getting access to jobs and education. The complex interplay of social, economic, and psychological elements that affect how internally displaced people IDPs adjust to new circumstances makes it difficult for them to manage. A number of things, such as ineffective government aid and challenges finding employment and housing, can lead to financial troubles.

Importance of Government's Reintegration Program

The Philippine government has worked hard to assist internally displaced people (IDPs) since the Marawi crisis, working with the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM). The focus of these initiatives has shifted from emergency response to early recovery, with an emphasis on economic possibilities, healthcare, education, and basic services. In order to meet the urgent needs of displaced communities and establish the framework for long-term rehabilitation, collaborations with agencies such as the UNHCR have proven crucial (UNHCR Philippines, 2017).

In order to promote economic recovery, the BARMM administration has provided disadvantaged IDPs with direct livelihood cash aid through its Marawi Rehabilitation Programs (MRP). Cash assistance from programs like the Bangsamoro Sagip Kabuhayan Project has allowed participants to start microbusinesses and start over. About 3,844 IDPs earned Php15,000 apiece by September 2022, while more than 500 others received Php5,000 each. These recipients addressed a wide range of

vulnerabilities and included widows, pregnant women, nursing moms, single parents, Islamic teachers, and returning Overseas Filipino Workers (Bangsamoro Information Office, 2022).

Many displaced people still rely on outside help in spite of these efforts, which emphasizes the necessity of allocating resources in a way that strikes a balance between humanitarian relief and long-term rehabilitation. In order to address important protection issues, especially for the most vulnerable groups, the government continues to work with agencies such as UNHCR, guaranteeing fair access to resources. Long-term recovery programs that empower IDPs and build resilience in impacted communities continue to be prioritized (UNHCR Philippines, 2017).

For disaster preparedness, response, recovery, and rehabilitation, a thorough framework has been established by the Philippine Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Act of 2010 (RA 10121). By requiring the establishment of disaster risk reduction and management councils (DRRMCs) at the local level, this law improves the country's capacity against disasters. The act increases resilience against natural and man-made disasters, such as those that occurred during the Marawi crisis, by incorporating disaster risk reduction strategies into local development plans and placing a strong emphasis on community involvement.

Supplementing RA 10121 is the Local Government Code of 1991 (RA 7160), which empowers local government units (LGUs) to oversee disaster planning and response activities. This law allowed LGUs to develop localized disaster risk reduction and management plans, addressing the specific needs of their communities during the Marawi Siege. Local authorities mobilized resources to provide food, shelter, and medical aid while organizing evacuation efforts and establishing centers for IDPs. These legislative frameworks underscore the importance of grassroots participation and community involvement in disaster management. Addressing the challenges faced by bakwits requires recognizing their resilience, reducing stigma, and fostering an inclusive environment for recovery (Climate Change Laws of the World, n.d.).

Anderson Villa and Amorisa Wiratri's work in 2023, "Rethinking Local Citizenship and Integration of Persons of Indonesian Descent in the Southern Philippines," offers a convincing analysis of the significance of local citizenship and the crucial role that the government plays in reintegration initiatives. Their research highlights the intricate interactions that occur in a globalizing society between the political, social, and cultural aspects of citizenship transition

The Tegtmeier Pak (2006) four conceptions of citizenship are briefly mentioned in Villa and Wiratri's paper. These include participatory citizenship, which focuses on the normative role of citizens in public life and good governance, and cultural citizenship, which supports a sense of social and cultural belonging in a particular polity. A number of migration scholars have examined the link between migrants and their host nation; in the Southeast Asian context, these academics include Olson (2007), Horvatich (2003), and Allerton (2017). The belief held by other nearby islands that the Sama Dilaut people do not practice Islam has prevented them from ever being fully assimilated into the Filipino culture, according to Horvatich (2003). Olson (2007) and Allerton (2017) investigate the marginalization of illegal migrants and their offspring in Sabah, Malaysia's national politics.

Furthermore, they contend that the issue of immigration is tied to both regional membership and legal identification.

The definition of integration given by Penninx and Garcés-Mascreñas (2016), which includes social transformation, settlement, and engagement with the host community, is followed in the study. As per their perspective, integration has three distinct components: the legal and political dimensions, which include rights to vote, citizenship, and legal residency; the socio-economic dimension, which includes access to housing, health care, education, and the labor market for immigrants; and the cultural-religious aspects. Complete integration in the host nation can be defined as the migrants' participation in their communities along those three axes.

Nearly same context of IDPs with their political migration, IDPs can benefit from a range of political, social, cultural, and economic possibilities. According to Doluda (2023), the movement of IDPs can influence the creation of new laws and policies that safeguard their rights and help them integrate into host cities. According to empirical research demonstrating encouraging trends in social integration, the social integration of IDPs can promote variety and strengthen the social fabric of host communities (Chuiko & Fedorenko, 2021). Cultural understanding and cohesiveness may be improved as a result of the IDP inflow through the sharing of cultural practices and information (Krakhmalova, 2019).

However, these opportunities are not without difficulties and contradictions. For example, the marginalization and lack of protection of rights that IDPs frequently experience might impede their ability to integrate politically and socially (Zetter, 2011). While IDPs might boost regional development and offer resource potential to certain places (Arakelova, 2017), they may also encounter serious job and financial difficulties that need for specific government assistance (Krakhmalova, 2019).

Political migration of IDPs can lead to beneficial changes in the political, social, cultural, and economic spheres. In order to fully utilize these opportunities, IDPs must overcome several obstacles, such as social injustice (Toole, 2019), mental health problems (Melnychuk & Klimovskyi, 2022; Schnyder et al., 2018), and the requirement for creative solutions to facilitate their integration and engagement in society (Doluda, 2023). Together, these efforts must be made in unison.

Technical Literature Case Study

The popular research methodology in the social and biological sciences is case study. Case study research has no universally accepted definition. All the same, a case study is essentially an in-depth study into an individual, a group of individuals, or a unit with the goal of generalizing over multiple unit. (Woods, 2017).

Scholars engage in discourse regarding the manner in which case studies explore intricate phenomena within their natural environments in order to enhance comprehension of said phenomena. In fact, Sandelowski (2010) suggested that the holistic nature of nursing care can be addressed in research by using case studies. A complex and wide-ranging topic, or phenomenon, can also be narrowed down into a manageable research issue(s) by the researcher by detailing the steps taken while using

a case study technique. Through the collection of both qualitative and quantitative datasets, the researcher gains a deeper understanding of the phenomenon than would be possible with the collection of only one type of data.

Instrumental Case Study

Stake (1995) recognizes the popularity of case studies in qualitative inquiry but argues that they are not 'essentially qualitative' or a methodology; rather they are delineated by the specific cases themselves. Stake specifically defines three types of case study one of which is instrumental. An instrumental case study aims to provide insight into an issue or refine a theory in which the case itself here is secondary and might be atypical of other cases. To borrow Stake's words, instrumental case study protocols provided us the freedom to select a case that "maximized what we can learn." He further explained that, "often an unusual case helps illustrate matters we overlook in typical cases."

It is important to note that the purpose of instrumental case studies is to understand and learn at a deep level about one specific case. In other words, instrumental case study allows researchers to gain an insider's view of an issue or concern. This was supported by Yin (2009), arguing that by focusing on 'how' and 'why' questions, as well as a contemporary phenomenon within a real-life context has led to an instrumental case study design.

Ravenstein's Theory of Migration

The phenomenon of bakwits, or internally displaced persons, from the Marawi Siege in City of Koronadal can be studied through the lens of Ernst Georg Ravenstein's theory of migration, which he proposed in his article "The Laws of Migration." A framework for comprehending the trends, driving forces, and effects of migration is offered by Ravenstein's theory, and this framework can be used to examine the political migration of bakwits in City of Koronadal. Researchers may learn more about the dynamics of societal changes, settlement, and displacement that follow such events by contrasting this modern phenomenon with Ravenstein's theory.

The laws of migration by Ravenstein highlight a number of important concepts that are pertinent to the study of bakwits in City of Koronadal. The notion of dispersion, which is the opposite of absorption, is one of the guiding concepts. Dispersion refers to the spreading out or scattering of people from their original location to various destinations. This gradual spreading out of migrants from urban centers to rural areas reflects the concept of dispersion. The attractive force of growing cities influences migration patterns, causing a ripple effect that reaches even the most remote corners of the country. Within the context of the Marawi Siege, the term bakwits may pertain to the act of relocating from their initial residences in Marawi to different locations, such as City of Koronadal, with the intention of seeking refuge and security. The idea that migrants gravitate toward industrial or commercial hubs is another aspect of the theory that may help to explain why bakwits might decide to settle in cities like City of Koronadal, where there may be greater options for support and a living.

An examination of refugee movements within the framework of conflict and persecution provides a clear illustration of the applicability of Ravenstein's law of migration to political science research. Since forced political migration takes the form of refugee flows, political scientists frequently investigate the causes and effects of these movements. By utilizing Ravenstein's principles, researchers can investigate the geographic dispersion of refugees, the variables affecting their migration, and the effects of the refugee crisis on receiving nations or communities. Through application of this theory as a framework for this investigation, researchers can reveal underlying causes of the 'bakwits' movement, including social networks, security vulnerabilities, and economic prospects.

Many insights can be gained by researchers studying the Marawi Siege bakwits in the City of Koronadal using Ravenstein's theory. They can determine how bakwits utilize opportunities provided to them and how it affects their patterns of settlement. Additionally, the theory can aid in comprehending how infrastructure, services, and support systems either help or hinder 'bakwits' as they integrate into their new surroundings.

Research Questions

Generally, the study aimed to describe and analyze political migration as experienced by the Marawi Siege bakwits in City of Koronadal through the lens of Ravenstein.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What were the factors that led to the political migration of Marawi Siege bakwits to the City of Koronadal?
2. What were the challenges encountered by the bakwits in their political migration and how do they cope with the challenges?
3. What were the opportunities that came with political migration and how do the bakwits deal with the opportunities?
4. Based on the findings, how may political migration be described?
5. How may the phenomenon of political migration be viewed through the lens of Ravenstein's Theory of Political Migration?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research study was designed as an instrumental case study. It concentrated on the Marawi Siege bakwits factors of political migration; the challenges they encountered and their coping strategies; the opportunities and how they dealt with them; their description of political migration; and the analysis of their perspective on the political migration through the lens of Ravenstein's theory. The researchers selected the instrumental case study design because they investigated how Ravenstein's theory was used as a framework to analyze the overall political migration to City of Koronadal of

Marawi Siege bakwits. Through this research design, the case was looked at an in-depth, its contexts were scrutinized, and it helped the researchers to pursue the external interest. The study involved a group of individuals who experienced the political migration phenomenon.

Setting

This study was conducted in the City of Koronadal, South Cotabato. It is located in Southern Mindanao, in the Province of South Cotabato. It is the seat of the provincial capitol of South Cotabato and the province's only city. Koronadal is currently a rapidly growing economic hub comprised of twenty-seven (27) barangays, including the poblacion's four (4) zones. Being the capital city of South Cotabato, it serves as the province's political, cultural, and socioeconomic hub. The researchers chose this particular setting because following Ravenstein's theory (1885), he postulated that bakwits or internally displaced persons are moving towards urban areas which are centers of commerce or industry because there may be more opportunities for livelihood and support.

Furthermore, afraid to be stuck again in the conflict between Philippine Army and Maute Group, whose true intention is to establish an Islamic State in Mindanao, 2017 Marawi Siege bakwits embarked to a long journey leaving for South Cotabato which is located in the southern part of the island and is occupied by Christian majority. On July 27, 2018, President Rodrigo Duterte signed R.A. 11054, also known as Organic Law for the Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (OLBARRM) replacing the Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) with the new Bangsamoro Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (BARMM), which would have greater fiscal autonomy, a regional government, parliament, and justice system placing its government seat in Cotabato City (Bangsamoro Transition Authority, n.d.). Years before the said law was passed, Region 12 (SOCCSARGEN) and Autonomous Region in Muslim Mindanao (ARMM) were referred as South-Central Mindanao where different regional government agencies are located in Cotabato City and were providing services for both constituents of Region 12 and ARMM.

According to the data made available by the Disaster Response Management Division of the Department of Social Welfare and Development Field Office XII as of July 4, 2017, about 444 families composed of 2,220 individuals have evacuated to the City of Koronadal during the Marawi Siege. Although there was no evacuation site for Marawi Siege bakwits in the city, all of them stayed with their family, close relatives, and even friends which makes them considered as home-based evacuees. After much inquiry, there were no present data about the total number of Marawi Siege bakwits in the City of Koronadal following the said date both on the end of Department of Social Welfare and Development Field Office XII and Local Government Unit of Koronadal.

Participants of the Study

The study's participants were bakwits in City of Koronadal due to the Marawi Siege in 2017. The study employed the referral technique wherein the researchers' recruit their research participants by asking them to assist in identifying other potential participants. Afterwards, the researchers had their initial visit to their prospect participants to ask about

their personal background and determine whether they fit to be a participant of the study. The following criteria were employed in selecting the six participants: First, they must be Maranao living in Marawi City before the Marawi Siege took place. Second, they were forced to evacuate due to the Marawi Siege and considered to be internally displaced persons. Third, they moved to City of Koronadal which is within the borders of the Philippines. Fourth, they were either unable or unwilling to return to Marawi City due to threats, insecurity, or lack of basic services and protection. Fifth, they were recognized by local authorities as Marawi Siege bakwits. Sixth, at present, they must be 25 years old and above or already of legal age during their migration seven years ago. Seventh, they must not be 65 years old or older during the conduct of this study, Eighth, they were mentally able and can effectively communicate their ideas and opinions regardless of language so long as the researchers can understand them all. Ninth, they must be literate or able to read and write. Lastly, they were willing to participate in the study and gave consent to be interviewed by the researchers. Others which do not fall as part of the criteria were not included within the scope of this research.

The six participants of the study have different contextual conditions. P1 is a 26-year-old female and Marawi Siege bakwit who is a market seller. P2 is a 55-year-old female and Marawi Siege bakwit who is a government employee and a widow. P3 is a 26-year-old female and Marawi Siege bakwit who became a barangay official. P4 is a 25-year-old male and Marawi Siege bakwit who is a fresh college graduate and a market seller. P5 is a 26-year-old female and Marawi Siege bakwit who is unemployed. P6 is a 47-year-old male and Marawi Siege bakwit who is a tricycle driver and a single parent.

Research Instrument

The instrument that the researchers used is an individual interview for the process of gathering the requisite information to describe the migration experiences of bakwits in City of Koronadal due to the 2017 Marawi Siege. Participants were asked to answer about 31 interview questions which mainly focused on the factors that led to their migration to Koronadal City, challenges they encountered, their coping mechanisms, opportunities and how they dealt them. One-to-one interview is a widely used method of data gathering in health and social research. Individual interviews are a helpful opportunity to obtain transparency into people's attitudes, understandings and perspectives about a particular phenomenon and may lead to an in-depth compilation of results.

Interview guide was used by the researchers as it provides flexibility to the interviewers and the responses of the interviewees would not be affected by the other candidates. Semi-structured interview was used by the researchers as questions were formulated ahead of time. It was also used to dive deeply into personal and often sensitive issues; and to discuss participants' opinions, emotions, and convictions about a specific subject. Participants were capable of expressing themselves in their own terms during the semi-structured interview. The guide questions that were asked is the researcher-made questions which undergone validation to check the reliability and validity of the questions in consideration of the research questions. The suggestions given by the validators were applied to the said guide questions.

Data Gathering Procedure

Researchers observed the community where the 2017 Marawi Siege bakwits are settled in to identify their current situation. Following their observation, researchers conducted their dry run interview with the bakwits to ensure the effectivity of their research instrument. They generated an initial analysis to have a preliminary data about the political migration experience of the bakwits. The researchers then sought permission to conduct their study from the Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences of Notre Dame of Marbel University. Once the researchers have obtained the necessary signatories, they proceeded to the place where Marawi Siege bakwits were inhabiting and interviewed those who belong to their established inclusion criteria to collect data.

The researchers followed the necessary ethical standards throughout the study and presented the consent letter to the participants following the interview. The researchers conducted an in-depth, one-on-one interviews with the six bakwits they have chosen, using their research instrument as a guide to gather the data they needed until the study is finished. Interviews were conducted in different settings and it took about 30-40 minutes for every participant. The researcher who conducted the interview used the Tagalog version of the interview guide and translated it to Maranao to better facilitate the response of the participants. Interviews with participants 1 and 2 were conducted last December 9, 2024, at 3:00 in the afternoon in the busy public market of City of Koronadal. While the interviews with participants 3, 4, 5, and 6 were conducted last December 14, 2024, at 8:00 in the evening in the comforts of their homes due to their unavailability during the day.

The bakwits discussed their migration experiences, including the challenges they encountered, coping strategies they applied, and the opportunities they came across with and how they took advantage of them. All data and information were gathered and recorded in an audio file, which were carefully analyzed. Participants did not receive payments beyond reimbursements for expenses incurred, if there was any, as a result of their involvement in the study. However, researchers gave them a token of appreciation for their invaluable contribution to the research study. Following the completion of the study, the recordings were deleted.

Data Analysis

In this research, interviews were recorded and transcribed verbatim. Participants were encouraged to use their own language to better express their own ideas during the interview, hence, researchers translated them into English and reviewed for accuracy. The researchers used Braun and Clarke's approach in analyzing the data because it provides clear and practical framework for conducting thematic analysis, which is arguably the most influential in the social sciences at least. The data have undergone four levels of analysis. Level 1 analysis was carried out by identifying the key text segments that addressed the study questions. They were highlighted and color coded based on what they answered, red for push factors, gray for pull factors, yellow for the challenges they encountered, green for their coping strategies, blue for the opportunities that came with their political migration, and purple for how they dealt those opportunities. The identified key text segments were tabularized and underwent the level 2 analysis. Words, phrases, or lines were reworded to convey their intended meaning. Additionally, concepts

that best encapsulated the developed meanings had to be identified and developed. In order to perform Level 3 analysis, the common or related concepts were grouped together, and the themes that best bind or categorize them were found.

In order to address the problem's specific statements, themes were developed. Because the study is an instrumental case study, it was critical that the analysis of the case be taken to the point where the issue of political migration as experienced and Ravenstein's theory of migration could be clarified and understood.

Limitations of the Study

The paper's title is "Political Migration to City of Koronadal of Marawi Siege bakwits: Seen Through the Lens of Ravenstein." Using in-person interviews as its method of gathering necessary data, the study was qualitative in nature. The research findings can only be applied to the participants of the study and not to all Marawi Siege bakwits in City of Koronadal. The researchers considered six Marawi Siege bakwits based on criteria established by the researchers, which served as the primary source of data. The research instrument was an interview guide based on the problem statements.

Accessibility of data and information about the profiles of the Marawi Siege bakwits in City of Koronadal is also considered as limitation of the study. The option of bakwits to decline participation owing to their hectic schedules or other personal reasons was another restriction on the study. Because the participants speak the language they are most comfortable with, Maranao, only one researcher—who is Maranao by origin—was able to conduct the interview and comprehend the majority of the raw data. The study's time frame, financial constraints, and the transparency of the named Marawi Siege bakwits in City of Koronadal were among its other inevitable limitations.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the study on the factors that led the Marawi Siege bakwits to migrate to City of Koronadal; the challenges they encountered and how they coped with them; the opportunities that came with their migration and how they deal with them; their description of political migration; and how their political migration was viewed through the lens of Ravenstein's. The succeeding sections were organized based on the sequence of the statement of the problems.

Factors that led to the political migration of Marawi Siege bakwits to City of Koronadal

This section discusses the themes which were generated from the answers of Marawi Siege bakwits and were classified into two constructs: push factors that compelled the Marawi Siege bakwits to leave Marawi City and pull factors that attracted them to migrate to City of Koronadal.

Unsafe Environment

Participants' testimonies reveal a terrifying reality marked by the constant threat of violence: the Marawi Siege, which began in May 2017, created an environment of

extreme danger that forced many residents, known as bakwits, to migrate to safer locations like City of Koronadal. Participant 6 described the chaos, saying, *"We heard many gunshots... the government and ISIS only gave us civilians a grace period of 24 hours."* The overwhelming presence of gunfire and bombings underscored the urgency to evacuate, as Participant 1 said, *"The siege is wide, there are bombing, guns, and almost everyone are involved"* The instinct to defend one's family and the fear of impending death became so strong that people had to put their safety first.

Ravenstein's theory highlights that push factors are aspects of one's own nation that force people to leave (Ravenstein, 1885). Accordingly, due to acts of violence, war, or political persecution people are forced to flee and seek for safety in other places (Niva et al., 2023). People believed their lives were in danger during the Marawi Siege because of the violent confrontations between government forces and terrorists linked with ISIS. This idea was eloquently expressed by Participant 6, who said, *"You can't do anything because even if you don't want to leave, you will be forced to because you will die there if you don't leave."* This fear and sense of urgency show how the decision to migrate was directly impacted by the dangerous environment.

The participants' reflections also reveal the emotional and psychological toll of living in such a dangerous situation: Participant 4 recalled, *"When the shooting started, we were still there at night. When the gunshots never stopped, we left."* The ongoing fear of being caught in crossfire or bombings overshadowed other factors, like the availability of food or shelter, and the decision to leave was not just about their own safety but also about the safety of their families, as mentioned by Participant 5, who stressed the need to evacuate for her children's safety. This collective experience of fear and urgency highlights the important role that an unsafe environment plays in driving migration, reinforcing the broader understanding of push factors in migration studies (Lee, 1966).

Figure 1. Push Factors that Compelled Marawi Siege Bakwits to Leave Marawi City

This section shows the analyzed data given by the bakwits which tackles the factors in Marawi City that compelled them to migrate to City of Koronadal during the 2017 Marawi Siege.

Cycle of Violence

In addition to causing extensive damage, the Marawi Siege also brought to light a long-standing culture of violence that has historically characterized the area, compelling many residents, or bakwits, to flee to safer areas such as City of Koronadal. As one evacuee put it, *"Most of us are like that... They leave and go to another place because there is always a rido."* This desire for a peaceful environment where children can grow up without fear of gunfire highlights the urgency of their migration, and the prevalence of violent clan conflicts, or rido, has made it necessary for families to seek safety in areas less affected by such violence.

The normalization of violence, especially through clan feuds and conflicts, as described by Participant 3, further highlights the urgent need for change. Participant 2 compared their experiences in City of Koronadal and Marawi City, stating that the culture of violence in Marawi was not just a backdrop but a defining aspect of daily life: *"Nothing is happening here... I have never encountered any shooting incident here." "The rido is about conflict between clans and families, Muslims to Muslims... it's just revenge."* The persistent cycle of violence not only endangered lives but also made it impossible for a community to be stable, which led many people to flee in search of a safer setting.

Forced migration, according to Lech (2020), is the movement of people who are driven to leave their homeland because of circumstances like persecution or war. This phenomena was most illustrated during the Marawi Siege, when families were forced to flee their homes due to the centuries-old history of warfare as well as the current fear of violence. The intricacy of the issue was further highlighted by Participant 3, who pointed out that the siege symbolized a conflict between government forces and insurgents as well as underlying frustrations within the population. The decision of many bakwits to migrate was greatly impacted by this complex culture of violence, underscoring the major effects of such societal problems on the lives of people and families who are looking for peace and security.

Political Instability

Many people were forced to evacuate to safer locations like City of Koronadal as a result of the Marawi Siege, which highlighted the region's extreme political instability. The intricacy of the situation was emphasized by Participant 2, who said, *"Actually, there is a conflict between... it's mixed with politics... the shooting continued so we evacuated."* The political context not only exacerbated the violence but also added to the sense of unpredictability as early assurances of a speedy resolution fell through. Families were forced to put their safety first and seek shelter elsewhere due to the worsening political climate, which was characterized by escalating tensions and military confrontation.

As the violence increased, the government's response further exacerbated the siege's political aspects. This proclamation of martial rule illustrates the government's attempt to reassert control amid worries of wider chaos, as participant 4 pointed out: *"they*

said at first that ISIS is not only going to Marawi... Duterte proclaimed martial law and the checkpoints tightened at that time." Many bakwits felt the need to flee, though, because of the impression of a politically heated struggle in which local complaints were entangled with more general ideological conflicts. The political implications of the siege illustrated the profound ways in which underlying problems with governance and power relations can affect migratory trends.

The historical background of Marawi's political instability is crucial to comprehending the reasons for this forced migration. The International Crisis Group states that the region's complex history of conflict and autonomy has created a unique political environment that frequently leaves residents susceptible to instability. Political factors, such as repression and conflict, have a significant influence on migration decisions, and Marawi's geographic importance as a hub for trade and education, as noted in the Amnesty International (2022), raises the stakes of political unrest, impacting not only local communities but also regional stability. In the end, the Marawi Siege demonstrated the significant influence of politics on migration by highlighting how political instability and the exploitation of local grievances by organizations such as the Maute, as noted by Hwang (2019), can push families to seek shelter in safer areas.

Economic Instability

In addition to demonstrating a serious political issue, the Marawi Siege caused major economic instability, which forced many locals, known as bakwits, to relocate to safer locations like City of Koronadal. The economic cost was profoundly expressed by Participant 2, who said, *"Our livelihood has been lost as in zero really... Our house was one of the ones that was destroyed by the explosions."* Families' sense of hopelessness was heightened by the destruction of homes and businesses, which left them without any means of support. According to Ravenstein, these economic difficulties are not isolated occurrences; rather, they are a reflection of larger trends in which poverty and unemployment heighten political unrest and affect migration choices (1885).

Participant 3 pointed out that the impact on local businesses was particularly bad, saying, *"no one died but only the businesses... were affected by being bombed."* The destruction of economic infrastructure made it impossible for many people to return to Marawi. The combination of destroyed property and disrupted livelihoods left families with a difficult decision: either seek stability elsewhere or stay in a devastated environment with little chance of recovery. Participant 1 further emphasized this sentiment, saying, *"We have no plans to go back there because we have nothing to go back to."*

For the bakwits, moving to City of Koronadal brought both opportunities and difficulties. They acknowledged the economic benefits of their new location, saying, *"In Marawi, the cost of living is high, but here it's lower... there are more job opportunities."* This contrast highlights how economic factors influence migration, as families seek better job prospects and more affordable living conditions. Participant 5 also mentioned the challenges they faced upon arrival, saying, *"It was hard because our income went back to zero... there were still a lot of bills to pay."* Krakhmalova (2019) emphasizes the economic aspects of forced migration by pointing out that migrants frequently have severe financial and employment challenges that need for particular government support. In the end, the economic instability brought by the Marawi Siege was a major factor in

determining the migratory patterns of several families looking for a more stable and prosperous future.

Interrupted Education

Along with causing severe political and economic disruption, the Marawi Siege also prevented many children from completing their education, forcing families to relocate to safer areas like City of Koronadal. As stated by Participant 4, *"My sister took me here because many schools were closed at that time,"* the conflict hindered access to education. As school closures threatened to impede students' progress, families' concerns about academic continuity became urgent. In the study of Wapaño and Dagalangit (2024), they put emphasis on the traumatic implications of the siege affecting the every day life of the people.

Participant 6 further highlighted the difficulties of learning in the face of unrest by asking, *"How can they study if there is trouble there?"* The ongoing fear of violence and instability allowed little time for academic endeavors, compelling families to put safety before education. This fact emphasizes how conflict can have a significant effect on the educational environment, where children are frequently the most at risk. It was evident from the threat of further violence that staying in Marawi could endanger not just their physical safety but also their chances for the future due to disrupted education.

Many bakwits fled to City of Koronadal in search of a more stable atmosphere that would support education. People frequently relocate in pursuit of new chances, including development in their education, as Kynsilehto (2022) points out. Families moved in the hopes of giving their kids access to schools and the opportunity to finish their education without worrying about violence or disturbance. Therefore, the choice to migrate was motivated by a desire to safeguard not only their immediate safety but also their children's future educational opportunities, demonstrating how interrupted schooling acts as a powerful motivator in the setting of forced migration.

Psychological Disconcertment

In addition to disrupting the lives of many locals, the Marawi Siege caused severe psychological distress, which led families to relocate to safer places like City of Koronadal. This fear was expressed by Participant 3, who said, *"it's scary because there's a Marawi siege, we're afraid that we might get hurt because of course we still have dreams."* The siege created a climate of panic and uncertainty where hopes for a peaceful future were overshadowed by the constant threat of violence. A major motivating element for families seeking to flee the psychological toll of living in a conflict zone was this pressure.

As stated by Participant 2, *"I was afraid that I might not see my children anymore."* With children scattered throughout various educational institutions when the siege started, the abrupt onset of violence during school hours added to the anxiety surrounding family safety. As stated by Participant 3, *"It's difficult because you're at the point where you can't get out... there are bombs... and then there's a lot of policemen hanging around."* This

overwhelming anxiety not only disrupted daily life but also contributed to a sense of hopelessness, making the prospect of remaining in Marawi unthinkable.

Families were struggling with the psychological effects of the siege as they made the painful decision to evacuate. The ongoing exposure to chaos and violence, including seeing armed groups and hearing gunfire, had a long-lasting effect on their mental health, as stated by Participant 4, who said, *"We left because we were too scared... If we don't come out we will die there."* Akhunzada et al. (2015) state that although some internally displaced people may exhibit resilience, many of them suffer from severe mental health conditions such as post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, and depression. Because they wanted both physical safety and a break from the emotional suffering caused by the siege, bakwits left Marawi in large numbers as a result of this psychological discomfort.

Family Ties

Numerous bakwits migrated to City of Koronadal during the Marawi Siege, largely due to the pull factor of family ties. Participant 2 highlighted the value of familial support, saying, *"Because my siblings are here... My sister and brother are here."* Having family members in a new place offers both practical and emotional support during a crisis, and this connection to family can act as a vital anchor, assisting people in navigating the difficulties of relocation and adjusting to their unfamiliar surroundings.

As demonstrated by Participant 4's story, *"My uncle told me to come here to my sister. At first, he told me that I would only be here for a few days, but after a while, they decided that I should study here."* This initial invitation turned into a more permanent arrangement, demonstrating how family ties can help integrate into a new community and provide stability in the face of chaos. Many bakwits found comfort in the idea of temporary refuge with relatives. For those escaping conflict, these familial ties provide a network of support that can facilitate the adjustment and increase their sense of security.

Participant 5 mentioned, *"After we went to Iligan to stay with my cousin, I met my husband now, who is from Koronadal."* This demonstrates how the process of seeking refuge can unintentionally lead to new connections and opportunities. The experience of migration can also result in the development of new relationships. Family ties are important pull factors that draw migrants to new areas, according to Ravenstein (1885). Hall (2011) adds emphasis to this by pointing out that one of the main causes of migration is family reunification. In the end, the close family ties that attracted bakwits to City of

Koronadal reinforced the value of family in the migration process by offering both immediate support and a sense of community and belonging.

Figure 2. Pull Factors that Attracted Marawi Siege Bakwits to Migrate to City of Koronadal

This section provides the analyzed data given by the bakwits which tackles the attractive aspects of City of Koronadal and pulled them into the city during the 2017 Marawi Siege.

Support

During the chaos brought on by the siege, the pull factor of support became an important driving force in the migration of numerous bakwits from Marawi to City of Koronadal. This dependence on family not only offered instant shelter but also made the adjustment to a new community easier, as Participant 2 recalled, *"The first time we evacuated to Iligan because my brother was there. But since my sisters were here, she took us and we have been staying here permanently until now."* The stress of moving can be considerably reduced by having sympathetic family members nearby, who can provide both practical and emotional support during a crisis.

As more bakwits sought safety, it became clearer how important it is to have a solid support network. The emotion expressed by Participant 6, *"Only here can someone help us. In other places we have no connection. How do we survive?"* highlights this need and highlights the significant influence that social networks have during unstable times. In new environments, people could find it difficult to find the resources and assistance they need to survive if they don't have any established ties. In City of Koronadal, family bonds served as a lifeline, helping bakwits deal with the difficulties of displacement.

Support from family members promotes a feeling of belonging in a new setting in addition to helping to address immediate needs. Community ties are strengthened when people can rely on their loved ones for support, whether it be in the form of practical assistance or emotional encouragement. For those who have been displaced by conflict, this is especially important because it helps lessen fear and feelings of loneliness. Lastly, the support which was provided in City of Koronadal was crucial in drawing bakwits, demonstrating how family ties may have a big impact on migration choices when crisis occurs.

Safety

Many bakwits from Marawi chose to migrate to City of Koronadal amid the siege's chaos, largely due to the pull factor of safety. As stated by Participant 3, *"Because, according to our relatives, many people live here, it's safe here."* City of Koronadal was seen as far safer than Marawi, which made it a desirable location for individuals in need of security. Families who have suffered the trauma of war need this guarantee of protection so they may concentrate on starting again without having to worry about violence all the time.

Family suggestions served to further reinforce City of Koronadal's reputation for safety. As stated by Participant 6, *"My brothers-in-law came here before the Marawi Siege... they said that we should stay here because it is beautiful here. They rescued us."* The prior relationships and encouraging testimonies from family members fostered confidence in the new site. This type of assistance not only offered instant protection but

also made bakwits feel safe and accepted, both of which are crucial elements in facilitating the adjustment to a new setting following the difficulties of relocation.

Additional factor in the bakwits' sense of security was the fact that many of them had previously visited City of Koronadal. According to Participant 2, *"I've been here before... we used to visit here when my kids were little."* Families were able to be confident in their new surroundings since they knew they had a support system in case they needed it. Niva et al. (2023) indicate that migrants seek refuge in safer places due to their desire for safety and protection. In this instance, City of Koronadal not only served as a haven but also as a community where bakwits could recover their sense of security and normalcy during the Marawi Siege.

Cultural Inclusivity

Many bakwits from Marawi who sought safety in City of Koronadal during the siege found that cultural inclusion was a strong appeal. As said by Participant 3, *"They say this place is beautiful, because Muslims like us who are from a different tribe are welcome."* This statement captures an atmosphere that values diversity and makes it simpler for displaced people to feel like they belong. According to Hwang (2019), the presence of multiple indigenous communities in City of Koronadal creates a multicultural environment that can help reduce the sense of loneliness that frequently accompanies relocation, especially when words like "bakwit" might make displaced people feel guilt or uneasy.

City of Koronadal's desirability is further increased by the idea that it is a cleaner and more peaceful place. According to participant 1, *"Actually they say that it is better here than Iligan because it is clean and peaceful."* This remark implies that, in addition to safety, The quality of life in Koronadal adds to its allure for bakwits. Interactions between various cultural groups are facilitated by the tranquil environment, which makes social integration simpler. *"It's better here in Marbel because it's peaceful and close,"* said Participant 6, reaffirming the notion that being close to a friendly community is essential for making the transition easier for migrants.

The idea that social integration of IDPs might benefit host communities by fostering cultural understanding and unity is supported by empirical study (Chuiko & Fedorenko, 2021). The social fabric of City of Koronadal may be strengthened by the exchange of cultural customs and knowledge brought about by the migration of bakwits (Krakhmalova, 2019). bakwits support a culturally varied community by navigating their new surroundings and encouraging tolerance and understanding among its constituents. In the end, City of Koronadal's cultural diversity acts as a crucial draw, allowing bakwits to start over in an atmosphere that is welcoming and supportive.

Employment

The possibility of finding work is a major attraction for bakwits who sought safety in City of Koronadal both during and after the siege. As one participant explained, *"Because my father has relatives here, so we stayed with them until he got a job at the DENR."* This relationship demonstrates how family relationships not only offer emotional support but also make it easier to obtain employment prospects. Families seeking to relocate may find that having family members who have secured jobs in the area is an

important consideration because it offers a means of achieving financial security in an unpredictable environment.

As further evidence of City of Koronadal's economic viability, Participant 5 said, *"It's not that I've already found a job, but things are better here. I tell my cousins to look for work here because it's easier, and the agencies are close by."* This sentiment highlights the availability of job resources in City of Koronadal, where a large number of employment agencies are concentrated. The Philippine Statistics Authority (2022) claims that City of Koronadal's allure to job seekers is increased by its status as the SOCCSKSARGEN region's regional hub for trade and commerce. According to the City Government of Koronadal (2020), the presence of business hubs and better infrastructure draws in more investors and businesses, which strengthens the labor market.

With the ongoing expansion of City of Koronadal's economy, the area has emerged as a hub for job seekers. More than 10,000 job opportunities have been created for residents as a result of investments in local infrastructure and industry, as Governor Tamayo noted in 2024 (South Cotabato News, 2024). The local populace gains from this economic stability, and it also attracts bakwits seeking a new beginning. When displaced people are making decisions, the possibility of work is a major factor, which makes City of Koronadal a desirable location for those looking to start over following the chaos of the Marawi Siege.

Challenges encountered by the bakwits and their coping mechanism

This section discusses the themes which were generated from the answers of Marawi Siege bakwits on the challenges they have encountered in their political migration and the coping mechanisms they employed to overcome those challenges.

Immobility

The process of bakwits migrating to City of Koronadal from Marawi was difficult, especially as regards to immobility. According to Participant 1, *"With our family, we planned to evacuate when... there was a bit of traffic on the road so we walked to get out of there."* When the situation became urgent, families were forced to leave their cars and walk across the dangerous roadways. Their physical immobility made it more difficult for them to carry personal goods and increased the stress of escaping an unsafe circumstance. Roadblocks, checkpoints, and the presence of soldiers made the evacuation logistics more difficult, as Participant 3 pointed out, *"Because where we live, there are still soldiers."*

The limited transportation options made the evacuation process much more difficult. According to Participant 2, *"We walked to Saguiaran. There is no car."* Families were compelled to transport necessities using their own physical strength due to the shortage of vehicles, which was very difficult in the scenario at hand. In addition, participant 4 stated, *"We had a hard time carrying the things because we knew we might not be able to return there."* The physical strain of packing and relocating, along with the emotional strain, created a strong sense of urgency and loss. Many families left behind

homes full of memories and possessions because they could only take what they could carry.

Figure 3. Political Migration Challenges of Marawi Siege Bakwits

This section presents the analyzed data given by the bakwits which tackles the challenges they have experienced during their migration from Marawi City to City of Koronadal during the 2017 Marawi Siege.

The bakwits' difficulties were made worse by the psychological repercussions of their abrupt relocation. The magnitude of the crisis was demonstrated by the fact that the fighting caused the displacement of almost 360,000 people, according to Amnesty International (2017). According to Thomas et al. (2008), internally displaced people frequently face extra challenges when adjusting to new surroundings, which can impede their ability to adapt. These difficulties were made worse by the pain of leaving their homes and the worry about their unknown future. *"I remembered that we were by batch,"* said Participant 1, highlighting the chaotic character of their departure and recalling the challenge of organizing transportation. The bakwits' perseverance was put to the test as they dealt with the psychological and physical challenges of migration, highlighting the complex nature of their search for safety in City of Koronadal.

Non-communication

Bakwits escaping the Marawi Siege found their evacuation to City of Koronadal made more difficult by the difficulties of non-communication. As participant 6 put it, *"We also couldn't call her because there was no signal,"* underscoring the breakdown in communication that isolated families at a crucial time. People were unaware of one another's safety and location, which led to a sense of urgency and panic as they were unable to contact loved ones or make arrangements because of inadequate connectivity. In addition to complicating the logistics of the evacuation, the interruption in communication made already extremely stressed families even more anxious.

The challenges of non-communication were made worse by the chaotic surroundings. The emotional turmoil experienced by families who felt compelled to return to potentially dangerous areas in order to find missing relatives is exemplified by the statement made by Participant 6: *"We haven't left there yet because we have been back and forth several times. We returned there for my sister who was left inside."* Their predicament became more complicated due to the uncertainty regarding the safety of their loved ones and their worry of choosing the wrong decision. As families struggled with the fear of separation during a crisis, Participant 5's story of his brother's reluctance to leave their mother behind demonstrates the emotional weight of the decision-making process.

Furthermore, the existence of multiple checkpoints posed obstacles that further complicated communication and movement: Participant 3 said, *"When we were about to leave... the checkpoint was terrible."* This statement captures the frustration and anxiety felt at these security points, where soldiers frequently interrogated evacuees, intensifying fears of being mistakenly identified as potential threats. Participant 4 underlined, *"Getting out there is difficult because there are many checkpoints,"* further confirming the idea that the evacuation route itself was laid out with obstacles, and as bakwits had to negotiate

these difficulties, the absence of clear communication made their journey to safety in City of Koronadal even more difficult.

Vulnerability

Strict security measures and the unstable atmosphere brought on by the ongoing fighting made bakwits even more vulnerable during their migration from Marawi to City of Koronadal. Participant 5 said, *"The soldiers were very strict; you had to show your ID."* This rigorous verification procedure made people go through a maze of checkpoints where they were continuously asked who they were. In addition to increasing stress levels, the requirement to show identity was a serious obstacle to mobility, especially for people who had misplaced or could not access their credentials in the thick of the confusion. Families were made even more vulnerable by the added load of expensive transportation, which made it challenging for them to travel safely.

A general feeling of uneasiness among the bakwits was also influenced by their fear of violent organizations like ISIS. Participant 6 said, *"At first ISIS will catch you. They will also make you swear."* This terrifying fact highlighted the danger that refugees faced because they were attempting to avoid both military surveillance and the threat posed by extremist organizations. Due to the fear of being apprehended and interrogated by both army and militants, evacuees frequently felt stranded in a hostile atmosphere, which made them feel extremely vulnerable. Participant 6's repeated travels back to checkpoints highlighted the physical and emotional toll of their circumstances and the grueling nature of their attempts to go.

The physical difficulties of the escape served as more evidence of their vulnerability. The second participant revealed, *"My daughter's nurse... put on my big clothes just to get out of there,"* illustrating the extent people would go to in order to avoid being discovered. Given that families had to traverse challenging terrain while facing the threat of violence, the act of hiking to safety without appropriate transportation highlights how precarious their circumstances were. At a time when safety and security were critical, their vulnerability was increased by the need to escape quickly and the physical constraints placed on them by their situation. For bakwits who were eager to migrate to City of Koronadal, the combination of tight security measures, the imminent threat of extremist organizations, and the physical difficulties of evacuation ultimately created a dangerous environment.

Government Negligence

Negligence on the part of the government, which left many without necessary assistance, greatly exacerbated the difficulties faced by bakwits during their move from Marawi to City of Koronadal. As stated by Participant 1, *"At that time, there was no financial assistance here, so Abie had to go home there to claim."* This remark illustrates how displaced people are frequently forced to look for resources elsewhere at considerable personal risk due to the absence of timely aid. In agreement, Participant 6 said, *"When the siege was happening, there was no help from the government."* The lack

of government assistance at such a crucial moment not only made them more vulnerable, but it also brought attention to the shortcomings in the crisis response.

Financial aid was only one aspect of the negligence; another was a more general disregard for the needs of the displaced. One participant said, *"Soldiers more on handling the mautes, they didn't prioritize the individuals."* This comment highlights the idea that military operations were more concerned with fighting insurgents than with meeting the humanitarian needs of people escaping violence. As stated by Participant 3, *"We really like, we're asking for help, like we're calling for help for foods and clothes."* Such grassroots assistance became a lifeline for many bakwits, highlighting the gap left by government inaction.

Additionally, their problems were made worse by the general lack of a legal framework to protect and aid IDPs. According to Phuong (2005), internally displaced people frequently do not have the same legal protections as refugees, which can make them more vulnerable in strange environments. In addition to cultural differences and the challenge of adapting to new surroundings, this lack of protection made it more difficult for them to reconstruct their lives and adapt (Ekoh et al., 2022). The fact that *"not everyone received government assistance,"* as stated by Participant 2, underscores the arbitrary character of aid that is conditional on one's proximity to local authorities. The government's carelessness during the Marawi Siege ultimately put bakwits in a vulnerable position, unable to handle a complicated web of difficulties without sufficient assistance or safety.

Economic Insecurity

A major obstacle that made the already vulnerable circumstances of the bakwits worse was the economic insecurity they experienced when they moved from Marawi to City of Koronadal. Participant 2 articulated the psychological impact of this insecurity by saying, *"Financially, we were struggling... I remember. Hay naku!... As in it's really hard because you're back to zero."* This statement captures the overwhelming sense of loss that many people feel when they lose not only their homes but also their businesses and means of subsistence. As they tried to start again, families frequently found themselves financially unprepared for the change, which increased their stress and worry.

Their incapacity to get basic essentials also brought attention to their financial vulnerability. As stated by Participant 6, *"You would only come out when you have money hidden."* Even individuals with substantial financial means were subject to restrictions; their spending was frequently limited by the possibility of unanticipated emergencies. With the additional statement, *"It's hard to eat... You don't have anything to buy,"* Participant 6 highlighted the harsh reality of having little money and the difficulty of providing food for families. In addition to having an impact on their physical health, Participant 3 observed that their incapacity to receive enough nutrition added to their general sense of hopelessness: *"It reached the point where your meal is not complete."*

The difficulties of economic instability were exacerbated by the new environment's logistical obstacles. *"Many stores are close so it is difficult to find food,"* noted Participant 1, suggesting that families found its adjustment even more challenging due to the dearth of resources. *"There were ten of us sleeping in a small room,"* one of Participant 6's

descriptions of the claustrophobic living arrangements, highlights the stress on mental health and family ties. As Krakhmalova (2019) notes, IDPs frequently experience a great deal of difficulty acclimating to their new environment, especially in regards to unstable finances and family dynamics. bakwits trying to start over in City of Koronadal faced a difficult environment due to the trauma of displacement and the further negative impacts of economic insecurity.

Psychological Management

The traumatic experiences that the bakwits had during their migration from Marawi to City of Koronadal had a significant impact on their psychological management. Participant 2 emphasized the overwhelming nature of their situation, saying, *"We didn't feel hungry anymore because the nerves prevailed. You would not look for something to eat because you forget."* This reaction highlights how psychological distress can overshadow basic needs, as the trauma of their circumstances can trigger a state of numbness that inhibits even the most basic responses to hunger. The psychological burden of displacement frequently causes a detachment from reality, which makes it difficult to prioritize basic needs.

Another major issue that the bakwits had to deal with was sleep deprivation, which fueled a vicious cycle of anxiety and hypervigilance. As recounted by Participant 6, *"There was no sleep because it was night when we left there. Something might happen on the way."* The existence of soldiers implementing Martial Law combined with the ongoing possibility of danger created an environment with constant awareness. People felt vulnerable and worn out as a result of this increased stress level, which was made worse by having to pass through multiple checkpoints. As they were compelled to face the reality of violence in their environment, Participant 1's description of panic amid gunfire—*"Panic really got over us"*—further demonstrates the extreme psychological strain that marked their journey.

Furthermore, the lingering fear for loved ones left behind added to the emotional toll experienced by the bakwits. Participant 3 expressed this concern, stating, *"There is still fear like concern for the others who were left there."* Such worries can lead to chronic anxiety and feelings of helplessness, making it difficult for individuals to adjust to their new environment. Akhuzada et al. (2015) note that while some displaced persons may demonstrate resilience, others face significant mental health challenges, including depression and post-traumatic stress disorder. The psychological distress experienced by bakwits highlights that their adaptation to life in City of Koronadal is not only hindered by economic and logistical issues but also by the mental health ramifications of their experiences, as noted by Krakhmalova (2019). It is essential to attend to their psychological demands in order to aid in their recuperation and assimilation into new societies.

Ingenuity

As they dealt with the difficulties of moving to City of Koronadal, the bakwits from the Marawi Siege showed incredible ingenuity in their coping mechanisms. As stated by Participant 3, *"Just getting along with others and understanding what's going on and*

survive." This statement highlights the value of community and demonstrates a collaborative approach to resilience, where shared experiences created a sense of

Figure 4. Marawi Siege Bakwits' Coping Mechanisms

solidarity among individuals who have been displaced. In the face of hardship, the capacity to adjust by depending on one another not only offered emotional support but

also made it easier to come up with practical solutions, demonstrating the strength of solidarity in tough times.

This section shows the analyzed data given by the bakwits which talks about the coping strategies they employed when they encountered challenges in the course of their migration process from Marawi City to City of Koronadal during the 2017 Marawi Siege.

The bakwits' migration efforts were greatly impacted by financial limitations, which led to creative solutions to problems. As recounted by Participant 6, *"I looked for money in Marogong so we could get a fare to get here."* This ingenuity demonstrates a proactive attitude in the face of uncertainty and indicates the extent people went to ensure their passage. Many bakwits had to abandon their belongings because they thought they would return, but they soon realized they needed to find other ways to survive. *"I have brothers who help us,"* said Participant 2, suggesting that family support was essential in overcoming financial obstacles. During their transition, this dependence on family members provided a vital safety net.

According to Hwang (2019), bakwits are shaped by shared experiences of trauma and uncertainty, which influence their coping strategies and identities. Moreover, research by Peevey et al. (2022) emphasizes the need for both social support and problem-solving techniques for IDPs to cope effectively. The theme of shared resources and mutual assistance emerged strongly among the bakwits as a key coping mechanism. Participant 5 noted, *"We have family support, so we don't have to struggle,"* while Participant 3 added, *"Help? It's just our relatives... it's like unity to survive."* These statements illustrate a community-oriented approach to resilience, where individuals pooled their resources and supported one another in times of need. Because of their close ties to their families and sense of community, the bakwits' ingenuity proved to be an invaluable lifeline during their difficult relocation.

Social Response

The bakwits' social reactions to the difficulties they encountered had a big impact on their coping mechanisms throughout their migration from Marawi to City of Koronadal. Participant 6 emphasized the proactive approach many took, noting, *"Those who we think are financially able, we would approach them and ask for help."* This dependence on community networks underscores the importance of social capital in handling financial challenges. Seeking help from people who are thought to be more capable highlights a collective resilience in which people bond together to help one another during difficult circumstances. This social reaction strengthened the ties throughout their society while also providing instant relief.

For many bakwits, the desire to put their children's welfare first was a strong motivator. In the midst of hardship, parents felt a strong sense of responsibility, as shown by Participant 6: *"We just thought about the children... No matter where we are, our lives are important."* This idea was further highlighted by Participant 2, who shared, *"When you see your children... You will be encouraged."* bakwits were inspired to persevere despite the enormous stress and uncertainty because of their emotional connection to their

children. In addition to offering a justification for surviving adversity, the emphasis on familial obligation also encouraged optimism for a brighter future.

Family members' emotional reactions were also very important in helping them deal with the anguish of being uprooted. The moving experience of fleeing Marawi was recalled by Participant 4, who said, *"I remember my mother and sister crying in the car."* This shared vulnerability fostered a safe space where emotions could be freely expressed and encouraged mutual reassurance. During a difficult period, their optimism that *"the siege will end and we'll be able to get back there complete"* displays a common vision for the future that lifted their spirits. As they negotiated the difficulties of their migratory journey, the bakwits' resolve was greatly enhanced by this social reaction, which was based on familial bonds and community solidarity.

Psychological Strategies

To deal with the stress and emotional turmoil of their circumstances, bakwits used a variety of psychological strategies during their journey from Marawi to City of Koronadal. As stated by Participant 1, *"While everyone was panicking, I remembered that my parents tried to calm us all down."* The family's proactive efforts to provide comfort, including purchasing food, acted as a psychological anchor in the midst of chaos. A sense of safety and normalcy was established by the act of soothing one another, which is essential in emergency situations. These techniques allow people to find comfort in shared experiences and emphasize the value of familial ties in coping with anxiety and terror.

Adaptive coping methods provide a fresh perspective on the psychological resilience exhibited by the bakwits. According to a research of Maruta et al. (2020), psychological therapies, such psycho-correction programs, can assist IDPs feel less depressed and anxious. Even though the bakwits might not have had official access to these therapies, their dependence on group assurance and family support can be viewed as unofficial resilience-boosting strategies. They were better equipped to deal with their anxieties and uncertainties by creating a supportive atmosphere, proving the human ability to bounce back from hardship.

Furthermore, for those who are suffering displacement, organized social services are essential to improving coping mechanisms. Programs for social rehabilitation and adaptation are crucial for helping IDPs create useful coping strategies, according to Pesotska (2022). Although the bakwits were supported by their close social networks, the provision of extensive psychological services would improve their capacity to cope with stress and trauma. In order to facilitate healing and rehabilitation and give people the resources they need to reconstruct their lives following such severe disruption, it is essential to recognize the psychological effects of displacement.

Faith

The bakwits' coping mechanisms during their move from Marawi to City of Koronadal were heavily influenced by their faith. In the midst of the confusion and uncertainty of their circumstances, they found solace and strength in prayer and faith, as demonstrated by Participant 3's statement, *"We were just praying that what—umm Allah will guide us, that he will protect us."* In addition to offering psychological comfort, praying

gave them hope and strengthened their conviction that they could find safety under divine direction.

The significance of spiritual resilience in the face of hardship is highlighted by the incorporation of faith into their coping strategies. In order to manage the psychological stress of displacement, many bakwits found that praying gave them back control over their situation. Invocations of faith can serve as a unifying force during times of distress, bringing families and communities together through common beliefs and hopes for better times to come. As a result, faith became an important part of their journey, providing them with a framework for interpreting their experiences throughout the Marawi Siege as well as psychological support.

Opportunities that came with political migration and how do the bakwits dealt with the opportunities

This section provides the opportunities that the Marawi Siege bakwits came across with their political migration and how they dealt with them.

Social Networks

Despite being prompted by push factors like violence and instability, the bakwits' move from Marawi to City of Koronadal also brought them a number of advantages, especially in the form of social networks. *"My brothers-in-law are here. They sheltered us when we first arrived here."* Participant 6 emphasized the support that came from family members, saying that their prompt presence not only offered a safe haven but also made the adjustment to a new environment easier. The bakwits were able to swiftly obtain the information and resources they needed to adjust to their new situation because they had family who were already established in Koronadal.

Social networks served more purposes than just providing shelter; they also offered helpful advice on how to start over. According to participant 6, *"They taught us strategies to make money and how to live here."* The bakwits needed this knowledge transfer to help them navigate new economic environments. Support from family members in obtaining jobs, including leasing a tricycle for livelihood, illustrated how crucial social connections are to building resilience and financial security. By empowering bakwits to develop self-sufficiency in their new home, these networks also relieved immediate financial strains.

Additionally, the experience of migration brought about unexpected social connections, as demonstrated by Participant 4, who was surprised to learn that *"we have many relatives here and I found friends here."* The strengthening of family ties and the development of new friendships helped to create a feeling of community and belonging in City of Koronadal. Reunification with family and the pursuit of economic opportunities are important drivers of migration, according to Hall (2011). These social networks turned into an invaluable asset for the bakwits, offering them practical help, emotional support, and a starting point for reconstructing their lives following displacement. The capacity to

utilize these relationships is a prime example of how hardship can foster the development of solid social ties that promote adaptation and development in an unfamiliar environment.

Figure 5. Political Migration Opportunities of Marawi Siege Bakwits

The figure presents the themes generated from the responses of the bakwits on the question about the opportunities they came across with on their political migration during the 2017 Marawi Siege.

Humanitarian Aid

When bakwits moved from Marawi to City of Koronadal, they received a lot of humanitarian aid, which was crucial in helping them adapt to their new situation. As stated by Participant 2, *"If you didn't have a green card at that time, you weren't a Marawi Siege evacuee."* The DSWD-issued DAFAC green card was crucial for gaining access to food distributions, guaranteeing that even those who weren't local voters received the assistance they needed. Humanitarian organizations' concerted efforts to meet the displaced population's urgent needs were evident in the systematic relief delivery, which was essential during such a trying time.

The bakwits encountered obstacles in spite of the aid, especially with regard to financial support. While basic requirements were satisfied, prospects for more complete financial stability remained elusive due to the lack of monetary aid, as stated by Participant 2: *"In Marawi, they have their first release of 73,000, 25,000, 50,000... But here there is no cash assistance, food only."* As evidenced by Participant 1's comment regarding returning home for relief distributions, the bakwits frequently had to go back to Marawi for extra support. This dependence on occasional assistance highlighted the continuous difficulties they encountered in finding a steady source of income in their new setting.

In addition, it became evident that many bakwits needed ongoing support as they dealt with the challenges of reconstructing their life. As stated by Participant 2, *"We haven't been notified yet that we can fix our house because we haven't been paid yet."* Similarly, Krakhmalova (2019) found that internally displaced people frequently face severe financial and employment challenges that require government assistance. Even though humanitarian help offered short-term respite, the bakwits' long-term prospects depended on more extensive support and chances for economic interaction in City of Koronadal. The interaction between aid and the pursuit of stability brought to light the difficulties in recovering for communities that have been displaced.

Employment Opportunities

Bakwits' migration from Marawi to City of Koronadal has significantly increased their employment opportunities, enabling them to build more stable lives. College graduate Participant 2 was resolute in her job search, saying, *"I really tried to apply. So by the mercy of Allah, I got it."* This is consistent with a larger trend identified by Kynsilehto (2022), where people frequently move in search of new opportunities and better living conditions. The successful transition into employment allowed Participant 2 to support their family and ensure that their children could receive an education, further emphasizing the role that employment plays in promoting stability.

As a hub for trade and business in the region, City of Koronadal draws people who want to capitalize on its growing market. As stated by Participant 2, *"My two siblings now have their house here because we found here the opportunities that were not in Marawi after the Marawi Siege."* This statement emphasizes the potential for economic engagement in Koronadal, which creates an environment that is favorable for families to prosper. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2022), this economic climate

attracts people who are keen to take advantage of new business opportunities, improving the general quality of life for bakwits.

Furthermore, the fact that people like Participant 6 continue to work shows how adaptable bakwits are in their new setting. He said, *"I was a driver there in Marawi, then I'm still a driver here."* Their assimilation has been greatly aided by their capacity to maintain careers and establish networks within the community. In 2024, Governor Tamayo highlighted the region's increasing economic stability by pointing out that over 10,000 job possibilities have been created for residents as a result of investments in local industry and infrastructure (South Cotabato, 2024). All of these elements work together to show how the migration experience enabled bakwits to start over in City of Koronadal by providing both immediate assistance in the form of humanitarian help and opportunities for long-term employment.

Economic Opportunities

Bakwits were able to reconstruct their life due to the economic prospects brought about by their move from Marawi to City of Koronadal. *"It took a long time because they were still looking for a good business to earn a living,"* said participant 1, referring to the early difficulties. As things improved, participant's mother started helping the family out with a variety of endeavors, such as running a restaurant and selling face masks. This flexibility demonstrates the bakwits' ingenuity in figuring out how to make money in spite of obstacles. Families frequently move to improve their socioeconomic situation in search of better opportunities in urban regions, therefore having an entrepreneurial spirit is crucial (Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations, 2023).

For many bakwits, being able to start their own businesses has changed their lives. *"The time we've been here, we've been able to build a house and businesses, and then we've started studying again,"* said Participant 3, underscoring the wider influence of economic opportunities on education and family stability, allowing people to make investments in their futures. As Participant 5 pointed out, *"Yes, there are also opportunities here,"* City of Koronadal has an atmosphere that encourages entrepreneurship. *"Any business you want to pursue is welcome here."* This openness encourages a culture of creativity and economic participation, which helps displaced people prosper.

Furthermore, the cost of living in Koronadal has been lower than in Marawi, which has improved people's quality of life in general. Participant 2 clarified, *"You can purchase rice, vegetables, and fish with 100 pesos."* If you do a comparison there? *"Your 100 pesos is not enough."* This affordability makes it easier for families to meet their basic needs, and the City Government of Koronadal (2023) has also put policies in place to encourage investment, like accelerating corporate processes and offering incentives, which further supports economic growth. All of these factors show how the migration experience has

given bakwits access to crucial economic opportunities, allowing them to rebuild not only their lives but also their communities in City of Koronadal.

Education

Due to the substantial educational opportunities brought about by the bakwits' transfer from Marawi to City of Koronadal, families are now able to pursue their scholastic aspirations and enhance their prospects for the future. The statement from participant 4, *"Now I have graduated from college and am just waiting to take the board exam next year,"* demonstrates how moving to a new setting aided in academic progress. As people frequently look for greater possibilities for learning and personal development, this pursuit of education is a common motivation of migration (Kynsilehto, 2022). Access to higher education not only empower individuals, but it also helps families and their general stability and growth.

Parents are clearly focused on education because they see it as a means of providing their kids with a better life. In her optimistic statement, *"My children, when they finish their education, they will look for a job here as well,"* Participant 2 emphasized the value of education in ending the cycle of poverty and paving the way for the prosperity of future generations. In addition, participant 2 expressed delight in helping their kids with their schooling, stating, *"That is my greatest accomplishment, in my opinion. Even though my husband is gone and my ATM is empty... it's okay."* This fortitude in the face of adversity is a testament to the transformative power of education and the resolve of parents to make investments in their children's futures.

"Even though life is hard, I can support their education even now their mother is gone," said Participant 6, who also talked about his dedication to supporting his children's education despite personal challenges. This commitment highlights how education can be a ray of hope for families who have experienced loss and displacement. Together, these bakwits' stories show that migration has given them a safe haven as well as fresh chances for education and development, allowing them to hope for a better future for themselves and their kids.

Political Freedom

In addition to offering them economic and educational opportunities, the migration of bakwits from Marawi to City of Koronadal has also promoted a sense of political freedom and community engagement. Participant 2 observed the difference in political stability, saying, *"Politics here is more quiet and peaceful maybe because majority of the people here are Christians and also we have many rido there."* This observation emphasizes the relief that many bakwits feel in leaving behind the political tensions and conflicts associated with their previous environment, allowing them to participate in civic life without the fear of violence or instability that frequently accompanies it.

Bakwits' sense of agency and belonging is further enhanced by their integration into the local political landscape. As one participant put it, *"Because we've been living here for a long time, it's like I've been a part of barangay-like things,"* indicating active participation in community governance, which not only helps displaced people feel like they belong but also gives them the ability to influence local decision-making processes.

Political engagement can be especially empowering because it gives IDPs a forum to voice their needs and goals, thereby overcoming the exclusion they may have experienced in their previous communities (Zetter, 2011).

While IDPs may not have the same legal protections as refugees, their presence in City of Koronadal has the potential to positively impact local governance, as their experiences and perspectives can help create more inclusive policies that address their needs as well as those of the wider population. In this way, the migration experience has not only provided bakwits with a place to escape conflict, but also with a chance to regain their political agency and actively participate in forming their new environment (Doluda, 2023).

Resourcefulness

The bakwits' migration from Marawi to City of Koronadal has required a high level of resourcefulness as they have had to overcome the difficulties of starting over. In reflecting on their early struggles, Participant 1 said, *"At first it was difficult because we started at Karinderya before this store. When we found out that there was a vacancy here, we immediately grabbed the opportunity."* This ability to seize opportunities reflects the adaptability and resilience that many bakwits have shown in the face of adversity. By actively seeking out and taking advantage of opportunities in the local economy, they have established the foundation for their stability and success.

As demonstrated by Participant 6's comment, *"You are trying all sorts of things you can make money and give you sustenance,"* resourcefulness has emerged as a crucial survival tactic among the bakwits. This proactive approach to entrepreneurship demonstrates their resolve to establish a sustainable livelihood in spite of early setbacks. In addition to offering financial assistance, taking part in other endeavors helps the community feel empowered and in control. This kind of resourcefulness fits in with the socio-economic aspect of integration described by Penninx and Garcés-Mascareñas (2016), which highlights the value of contributing to the host community and having access to the labor market.

In addition, Participant 2 demonstrates the bakwits' ingenuity by saying, *"I feel like I will not be an employee and I'm still doing business."* The statement *"Our life here is better because I seem to have used what I finished in college"* demonstrates how people use their training and abilities to pursue business endeavors rather than regular jobs. By doing this, they enhance their sociocultural fabric and economic status in City of Koronadal, which helps them integrate even more easily. In addition to highlighting the bakwits' dedication to starting again, this holistic approach to resourcefulness shows how they have turned obstacles into chances for personal development and community service.

Economic Adaptation

Bakwits' migration has led to a great deal of economic adaptation as they work to support their families and adjust to their new situation. This resilience is demonstrated by Participant 6, who says, *"I used my income to pay for our needs and for my children's*

education." Bakwits urgently need financial stability, and this dedication to putting necessities first is evident. Their willingness to adjust economically is vital in a

Figure 6. Marawi Siege bakwits Dealt with Opportunities

new environment where they must establish themselves and sustain their families despite the hardships of displacement.

Figure 6 presents the themes generated from the responses of the bakwits on the question about how they dealt with the opportunities that came across with their political migration during the 2017 Marawi Siege.

Individuals must frequently assume several roles and duties in order to adapt to economic changes, as demonstrated by Participant 6's work schedule. *"I ride every night,"* he explained. This commitment to working long hours shows the extent to which bakwits go in order to secure their livelihoods. I return the tricycle before twelve midnight, and I ride again at three in the morning. They are able to create revenue and integrate into the local economy more easily as a result to this flexibility. The integration process, which includes social transformation and interaction with the host society, heavily relies on the ability to manage various economic activities (Penninx and Garcés-Mascreñas, 2016).

Bakwits in City of Koronadal are benefiting the local community in addition to ensuring their own well-being through their economic adaption. Their attempts to provide for their families and put money into their kids' educations reflect a larger dedication to creating a secure future. Their sense of belonging is strengthened as they develop relationships and learn how to use community resources and the local market. The bakwits' tenacity in striving to establish fresh prospects and a higher standard of living in their new community is demonstrated by this dynamic process of economic adaptation.

Improvements

Their ability to grasp possibilities has been a major factor in the notable improvements in the lives of bakwits who have migrated from Marawi to City of Koronadal. This dedication to education reflects a strong desire for upward mobility and the belief that academic achievement can pave the way for a better future. Participant 1 discussed the impact of these opportunities on their family, saying, *"To my parents, they used those opportunities to improve our lives and let us, siblings, go to school."* These improvements have been made possible in large part by the capacity to find employment and start businesses, which enables families to make investments in the education and welfare of their children.

Their attempts to establish sustainable livelihoods demonstrate the bakwits' spirit of entrepreneurship. *"I used the business so that I could survive here and so that if I needed or wanted to buy something, I could buy it with my income,"* said Participant 4, indicating a proactive attitude to handling financial affairs and a strong awareness of the significance of economic self-sufficiency. In addition to bettering their own situation, bakwits contributed to the local economy by starting enterprises. Given the substantial obstacles IDPs frequently encounter when acclimating to new contexts, such as problems with employment, housing, and financial stability, such adaptability is crucial (Krakhmalova, 2019).

The improvements made by bakwits represent a change in their general quality of life and go beyond simple financial security. According to Participant 1, their family now owns two houses, which represents stability and safety in their new neighborhood. This

development demonstrates the bakwits' determination and resourcefulness in overcoming their situation. They have created a nurturing environment for their family by taking advantage of educational and career opportunities, demonstrating the possibility of notable advancements even in the face of hardship. The bakwits' shared experiences show how their migration path has resulted in significant improvements to their lives and future goals.

Social Belonging

The bakwits' relocation to City of Koronadal has given them access to economic and educational opportunities, but it has also given them a strong feeling of community. In support of this idea, Participant 3 said, *"Like we are able to help here..."* Since bakwits use their past experiences to make positive contributions to their new surroundings, this reflection emphasizes the strong bond they have with their community. *"When you feel happy as if you are helping others, then what do you know about yourself that you once also experienced hardship like during the Marawi Siege."* They can build relationships with others by engaging to initiatives that promotes the community, which is essential for their social and emotional health.

A crucial element of integration is social belonging, which includes the sense of identity and community that people form in their new surroundings. According to Penninx and Garcés-Mascreñas (2016), social change and interaction with the local population are equally important to successful integration as economic involvement. The bakwits' dedication to becoming involved members of City of Koronadal is demonstrated by their readiness to share their knowledge and expertise with their community. This interaction strengthens the social fabric overall by fostering understanding and unity between various groups.

Additionally, as Doluda (2023) points out, the existence of bakwits in Koronadal may have an impact on regional laws and customs. Their input and experiences have the power to influence new legislation that upholds their rights and promotes their continued assimilation into the host community. In addition to bettering their personal lives, bakwits foster an inclusive and resilient culture as they forge their identities and responsibilities within the community. Their journey from displacement to belonging thus exemplifies the transforming potential of social interaction and community involvement, enabling individuals to reconstruct their lives while strengthening the community in which they live.

Description of Political Migration

Marawi Siege bakwits' political flight from Marawi City to City of Koronadal was a difficult, desperate, and urgent journey. As the siege progressed, families had to leave their houses due to the growing conflict and violence. Without any plan, many fled the immediate threat to their safety, many abandoning their belongings and livelihood. The impulse to protect those you love and seek safety in a safer environment was the driving force behind the decision to migrate. A lot of bakwits in Koronadal relied on family ties, which gave them hope and direction in times of need.

When the bakwits tried to flee Marawi, they encountered numerous challenges. Checkpoints and the military presence added to the chaotic environment produced by the

siege. As they made their way through once-familiar but now dangerous areas, participants described the anxiety and uncertainty that followed their departure. Their move was made more stressful by the psychological toll of abandoning their homes and the uncertainty of what was waiting for them in Koronadal. Many bakwits cried over the life they had to leave behind in Marawi and felt a sense of loss and despair.

Upon reaching Koronadal, the bakwits faced more challenges as they attempted to integrate into the new environment. Since many of them had their occupations in Marawi City, losing their livelihood was a major hardship. Feelings of loneliness and concern about their future resulted from the emotional toll of displacement, which exacerbated the economic instability they already experienced. Accessing necessary services and resources was made more difficult by the unfamiliarity of their new environment, which made their transition process even more challenging.

The bakwits used a variety of coping strategies to deal with these difficulties and adjust to their new reality. Their reliance on social networks—especially family members who had already made Koronadal their home—was a vital component of their resiliency. These relationships not only offered them short-term accommodations and assistance, but also helpful advice on how to adjust to their new surroundings. The significance of community was emphasized by the participants, who emphasized how mutual support and shared experiences helped individuals who were displaced feel included and united.

The bakwits also showed incredible resourcefulness and adaptability in the face of hardship. They worked together to rebuild their lives, exchanging information and tools to get over challenges. In addition to providing helpful solutions to problems they face on a daily basis, this collaborative attitude strengthened emotional support, which helped them deal with the trauma of their experiences. The bakwits demonstrated the strength of communal ties in the wake of conflict and displacement by establishing a foundation for recovery through their solidarity and resilience.

Political Migration of Marawi Siege bakwits Through the Lens of Ravenstein

Ravenstein's Theory of Migration, which highlights the impact of political factors on migration patterns, provides an effective framework for analyzing the phenomenon of political migration among the Marawi Siege bakwits. According to Ravenstein's theory, political instability, persecution, and conflict are some of the push factors that frequently cause migration. People had to leave their homes immediately in search of safety during the Marawi Siege because of the violence that broke out and the subsequent imposition of martial law. The bakwits' relocation to City of Koronadal serves as an example of how political situations can force people to flee their familiar environments in search of safety and security.

In order to comprehend the migration of bakwits, Ravenstein's idea of dispersion is especially pertinent. These people dispersed as they left Marawi, with many taking sanctuary in cities like City of Koronadal because they felt safer there and had easier access to resources. This movement is a reflection of the larger pattern of displaced people moving to places that offer better chances for integration and support. The experiences of the bakwits demonstrate how political migration is a complicated process

that is impacted by both the sociopolitical environment of their new surroundings and the sociopolitical context of their former homes.

Furthermore, Ravenstein's theory emphasizes how important social networks are in determining migration choices. To ease their transition and adjust to a new life, the bakwits frequently turned to their preexisting connections in City of Koronadal. These networks gave them vital support networks that enabled them to overcome the difficulties of integration and displacement. The way that social dynamics and political factors interact shows how the bakwits' experiences fit Ravenstein's ideas, showing how migration is influenced by both the short-term need for safety and the long-term hopes for community and belonging.

Looking at the political migration of the Marawi Siege bakwits through the lens of Ravenstein's Theory of Migration reveals the complex relationship between conflict, political instability, and migration. The analysis of these people emphasizes how political conditions play a crucial role in influencing migration and how social networks help people adjust to new situations. This analysis adds to the larger conversation on the dynamics of political migration in conflict and displacement contexts while also deepening our understanding of the bakwits' experiences.

Formulated Conceptual Framework

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers come up with the formulated conceptual framework to encapsulate all of the themes and show their interconnectedness making it as a one cohesive narrative of bakwits having shared experiences of political migration to City of Koronadal because of the 2017 Marawi Siege. These themes were generated from the six Marawi Siege bakwits cases on the factors that motivated them to migrate; the challenges they encountered and coping mechanism they employed; and the opportunities that came with their political migration and how they

dealt with them. Through the use of this visual narrative, it showcased the insider's view on the political migration phenomenon using the case of Marawi Siege bakwits.

Figure 7. Formulated Conceptual Framework on the Political Migration to City of Koronadal of Marawi Siege Bakwits

Conclusions

The analysis of the Marawi Siege bakwits makes a strong case for using Ravenstein's Theory of Migration to look at the nuances of migration. Push elements like persecution and insecurity, as well as pull factors like the desire for better economic prospects, were the main drivers of the bakwits' political movement, according to the first proposition. This is in line with the study's findings, which show that one of the main reasons they moved to City of Koronadal was the apparent danger of violence in Marawi City. Ravenstein claims that unfavorable circumstances force people to migrate, and the urgency of fleeing violence supports this claim, so confirming the theory's applicability in this scenario. Although the study affirms the significance of these factors, it also draws attention to the psychological effects and emotional toll of such displacement, which are not adequately covered by Ravenstein's framework.

The bakwits' struggles, like as social marginalization and economic instability, are highlighted in the second proposition. They overcame these difficulties by using adaptation strategies and community support. Ravenstein's hypothesis, which recognizes that migrants frequently face challenges in their new contexts, is consistent with this observation. But the study shows that the bakwits were resilient and had agency since they actively looked for answers through their social networks. This is an obvious response of the bakwits as Filipinos value eastern perspective that leans towards collectivism. Family whether it be immediate or extended in the Filipino culture is always emphasized as part of one's own identity, hence maintain close ties in spite of crisis such as the 2017 Marawi Siege in the context of the bakwits. A more passive view of migration, on the other hand, contends that although migration is inherently difficult, the bakwits' proactive strategy for overcoming these obstacles is an important component that Ravenstein's theory might miss.

According to the third proposition, the bakwits made use of social networks to find employment in City of Koronadal, where political migration provided access to resources and improved living standards. This is in line with the study's findings, which show how the bakwits' transformation was aided by their ties to their families and communities. However, Ravenstein's approach may understate the importance of social capital in influencing migratory experiences because it mainly concentrates on geographic dispersion and economic incentives. The bakwits' need on well-established networks for support and direction highlights the value of social ties in migration, implying that these relationships may be just as important as financial opportunities in deciding how well migrants succeed in their new settings.

Political migration, according to the fourth proposition, is a complicated interaction between the desire for stability and better living conditions and forced migration. This complexity is clear in the study, which depicts the bakwits' migration as a calculated step toward a more secure future as well as a flight from danger. The emotional and psychological aspects of migration may not be well captured by Ravenstein's theory, despite its recognition of its dual nature. By weighing the advantages and disadvantages

of their relocation, the bakwits demonstrate the complexity of their situation and demonstrate a deliberate decision-making process.

The study supports the fifth proposition, which links the bakwits' migration to Ravenstein's theory by showing how their movement is a response to both push and pull factors, highlighting larger migration patterns influenced by sociopolitical settings. However, the findings also demonstrate that individual stories and community dynamics play a significant role in shaping migration patterns, suggesting that while Ravenstein's theory provides a useful framework, it may benefit from incorporating a more nuanced understanding of the social and emotional factors that influence migration decisions. The study's overall findings emphasize the necessity for migration theories to change and adjust to the complexity of human experiences when compelled to relocate.

Recommendations

There are significant implications for comprehending political migration through Ravenstein's theory from the qualitative investigation of the Marawi Siege bakwits in City of Koronadal. In addition to pull factors like safety, shelter, and community support, the propositions imply that push factors like violence, conflict, and insecurity are the main causes of migration. This theoretical framework highlights the need to address the underlying causes of displacement, suggesting that effective interventions should concentrate on reducing the circumstances that force people to leave their homes. By demonstrating that the bakwits' migration was in fact a direct reaction to the immediate threats posed by the siege, the study's findings support this idea and validate the applicability of Ravenstein's theory in examining their experiences. Since these actions could greatly lessen the need for forced migration, this alignment suggests that policymakers should prioritize conflict resolution and community stabilization initiatives in areas prone to violence.

The study does, however, also uncover a more nuanced story that goes beyond the original motivations for migration. The findings demonstrate the bakwits' adaptability and resilience in overcoming these challenges, even though the propositions draw attention to the difficulties they face, including resource scarcity, loss of livelihood, and cultural adjustment. This contrast suggests that migration should be seen as a dynamic process in which people actively look for chances for integration and community building rather than just as a response to unfavorable circumstances. Policies intended to aid displaced populations should give priority to the creation and fortification of social networks, as demonstrated by the bakwits' ability to utilize community support and social networks in City of Koronadal. Stakeholders can ease the transitions of migrants and improve their general well-being and integration into the host community by creating conditions that allow social capital to grow.

Furthermore, contrary to a more deterministic interpretation of migration that could be drawn from the propositions, the results show that the bakwits faced both opportunities and difficulties in their new surroundings. Because of this complexity, migration experiences are not all the same; rather, they are influenced by a wide range of factors, such as the host environment's sociopolitical context, community dynamics, and individual agency. The study emphasizes that although the bakwits encountered many challenges, including negotiating cultural differences and bureaucratic systems, they also

discovered opportunities for empowerment through entrepreneurship and education. This implies that interventions ought to be modified to identify and capitalize on the strengths of displaced people, fostering their agency and motivating them to actively engage in their new communities. Policymakers can help migrants not just survive but also thrive by offering them resources and support for economic opportunities and skill development. This will change their status from aid recipients to active members of their new communities.

The study's focus on social networks' contribution to the migration process also has significant implications for practitioners and policymakers. According to the assertions, social networks are essential for effective integration, and the results demonstrate how much the bakwits depended on them to get by in their new lives. This awareness emphasizes the necessity of focused assistance initiatives that promote ties within the community and offer tools for accumulating social capital among displaced people. The integration process, for example, can be greatly improved by programs that support community involvement, mentorship, and cooperative projects. The resilience of migrants and the results of their overall integration can be improved by stakeholders funding projects that fortify these networks. Through promoting diversity and cross-cultural interaction, this strategy not only helps the migrants but also enhances the host communities.

The juxtaposition between the propositions supported by Ravenstein's theory and the study's actual results emphasizes how complex political migration is. It highlights how critical it is to address the underlying causes of displacement while simultaneously acknowledging the agency and adaptability of migrants in their new settings. More effective policies and interventions that not only address the immediate needs of displaced people but also give them the tools they need to succeed in their new communities can be informed by this thorough understanding. In the end, stakeholders can support more inclusive and sustainable migration outcomes by taking a comprehensive approach that takes into account both the opportunities and challenges presented by migration. This will promote a sense of community cohesion and belonging that is advantageous to all parties.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Before conducting the interviews, the research paper was subjected to the Ethics Review Board to ensure that the study adhered to the accepted ethical standards. Researchers adhered to a one-on-one, in-person interview protocol. Participants of this study belong to vulnerable groups and hence participation in this study was purely voluntary as researchers estimate that the potential risks of this study were minimal. Participants may experience some psychological discomfort when answering questions about their process of moving to the City of Koronadal.

As a result, each participant was asked for informed consent via letter that includes their rights to agree or refuse to be interviewed which was adapted from the National Ethical Guidelines for Health Research 2022. They were asked to sign at the end of the informed consent to ensure the validity of their voluntary participation. Participants were still free to leave at any moment and without explanation after signing the consent form. Any relationship they may have with the researcher was not affected if they have

withdrawn from this study. If the interview has already taken place, the data gathered from it was not erased or destroyed immediately. The interviewee may request that the information they provide will not be used in the research study.

Furthermore, the research adviser accepted and signed a letter authorizing individual interviews, with the Dean of the College of Arts and Sciences, Notre Dame of Marbel University attached. It further specified that their identity was kept secret, researchers pseudonymized their identifiable information in the presentation of data. All responses utilized for academic purposes were treated with utmost confidentiality. Moreover, to achieve the maximum impact of the study especially to its stakeholders, only the final findings of the study were disclosed to publication or conference. Aside from the researchers, only the participants have the access to the raw data.

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